

Data-Aware Service Composition

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Chapter 1

Introduction

In the last decade, the prominent trend in software architecture is to build independent software components, called Web services, that are accessible through the Internet environment. The huge amount of available Web services suggests to assemble a desired application from a set of appropriate existing services and no longer writes it manually. Furthermore, Web service composition has enormous potential in streamlining business-to-business or enterprise application integration [34].

*Services*¹ (or Web Services, or e-Services as often referred to in the literature) are software systems offered by service providers in order to be composed and reused in a distributed, web-based environment. They are self-contained, modular applications that can be described, published, located and dynamically invoked, in a programming language independent way [15]. Services perform actions, which can be anything from simple requests to complicated procedures, e.g. submitting an on-line application for a bank account or modifying an airline ticket order. They allow to expose over the Internet (or intra-net) the core competencies of an organization by using standard languages and protocols. Services are characterized by constraints on the possible sequences of actions they can perform, that are called *conversations*. An example of conversation is represented by the procedure for booking a flight, an airline ticket order can be confirmed only if the user has sent the flight details.

Service-Oriented Computing (SOC) is the computing paradigm whose basic elements are services, used as building blocks to devise other services [30]. Service-Oriented Computing aims at building a world of collaborating services that are being loosely coupled to flexibly create dynamic business processes and agile applications, distributed within and across organizational boundaries and computing platforms. *Service-Oriented Architectures* (SOAs) are developed for realizing the SOC purpose, mainly consist of a middleware that enables the discovery, utilization, and integration of services. SOC/SOA aim to separate software engineering from programming, to emphasize on software engineering,

¹With the generic term “*Service*” we refer to any application component accessible in a programmatic way, Web Services are the most common examples.

and to deemphasize on programming. In this scenario, we can identify three basic roles:

- *Service providers* that use a programming language to build program components, all of these wrapped with open standard interfaces;
- *Service brokers* that allow services to be registered and published for public access;
- *Application builders* (or *Service Aggregators* as sometimes called in the literature to emphasize their mission) no longer create software from scratch using basic programming language constructs; instead they specify the application logic in a high-level workflow specification language, using standard services as components. They are organizations that compose multiple services into a new, single composite service offering.

The accumulation of available services over time will make it possible to find almost any desired component services. Thus, the job market demand is shifting towards high-level composition modeling skills for application building through composition of reusable services [35].

1.1 Service composition

In the service oriented approach, a service can be interpreted as a procedure (or method) in programming languages, therefore, a set of services as a sort of programming library. This similarity is the basis of the service composition problem: as exactly as in a programming language procedures/methods are combined to produce more complex procedures/methods, so services can be combined to build more complex services.

Service Composition is the problem of automatically combining a set of available services (often called *community* of available services), so to synthesize a more complex service, according to a desired specification (called target service or simply *target*). The latter is a *virtual* service, therefore fragments of its computation must be delegated to available services.

Example 1.1.1. For example, consider the steps that a traveler need in order to plan a vacation: first the destination must be chosen, then the traveler should find how to get there (by train, by car, by bus etc.) and where to stay (an hotel, an apartment, an hostel etc.). A company may want to offer a new service that assists the traveler in every step of his/her planning. The specification of the new service could be:

1. List the available destinations and let the user choose one of these;
2. Let the user insert the vacation details (the departure day, the period, the departure place etc.);
3. Show all the means of transport that reach the chosen destination;

4. Make the reservation for the chosen means of transport, if necessary;
5. List the accommodations available in the chosen destination;
6. Book the chosen accommodation.

Each of these tasks may be already accomplished by many services (e.g. on-line booking services of airway companies, travel advisor services etc.), therefore it results convenient to reuse these existing (and available) services. These services should be opportunely invoked to realize the target, it means that whenever the new service wants to execute an action there must exist an available service that can execute the desired action. In the travel planning example, steps 1,2,3 and 5 can be delegated to an on-line travel advisor service; whereas step 4 can be delegated to the booking service of the desired mean of transport; and finally, step 6 can be delegated to the booking service of the chosen accommodation. It is important to note that steps 4 and 6 may involve different services depending on the user choices, for instance, in step 4 a flight booking service must be invoked if (s)he chooses the airplane or a train booking service if (s)he prefers the train. ■

Service composition problem involves two different issues:

1. *Composition synthesis* (or simply composition) is concerned with synthesizing a new composite service, thus producing a specification on how coordinate available services to obtain the target service, i.e. for each possible situation (calculated on the basis of possible user choices) the synthesis specifies which available service must be invoked to execute a desired action of the target service. The synthesis can be obtained either *automatically*, i.e. using a tool that implements a composition algorithm, or manually by a human that calculates all the cases.
2. *Orchestration* is concerned with coordinating available services (by monitoring control and data flow among them) in order to guarantee the correct execution of the composite service (synthesized in the composition phase).

A number of approaches have been proposed to tackle the service composition problem. Most of them are inspired by the researches in cross-enterprise workflow and AI planning [32].

Orchestration has been widely addressed by other research areas, and most of the work on service orchestration is based on research in workflows.

1.1.1 The “Roman Model”

One of the most significant and influent approaches to service composition is the so-called “*Roman Model*”, in which service behaviors are abstracted as transition systems [14, 12, 31, 15, 22]. This proposal focuses on an abstract notion of activities (without modeling how their execution impacts the world), and model services as finite state automata with transitions labeled by these activities.

The model introduces a simple form of data-awareness that allows to represent finite-state data structures (e.g. a set of variables that range over a finite set of values). Precisely, in addition to available services, a community contains a so-called finite-state *data box*, i.e. an additional transition system modeling the evolution of a shared data structure whose state is affected by the execution of the activities of the available services. The data box can capture situations where services deal with data over finite domain.

The framework proposes a sound and complete composition algorithm that takes as input a set of descriptions of existing services, and a desired behavior (or “target” behavior) and provides as output a composition synthesis. The algorithm is based on the notion of simulation [25]. Intuitively, the existing services “simulate” the target service if, whenever the target is able to execute an activity, there always exists an available service that can execute that activity. Moreover, the framework proposes an algorithm that synthesizes an orchestrator program.

It is proved that the existence of compositions can be checked in polynomial time in the size (number of states) of the available behaviors and of the target behavior, and in exponential time in the number of available behaviors.

A concrete case of application of automated service composition with the Roman Model has been performed in the SM4All² EU research project, recently and successfully concluded [22].

1.2 Describing service behavior

In order to face the composition problem, formalisms are needed to describe the behavior of services, which is often called *process*. A (business) *process* can be seen as a collection of inter-related activities (or, in our context, actions) that collectively lead to an outcome [23]. This modeling task is strongly related to the research on Business Process Modeling (BPM). The research areas on BPM and SOC/SOA are strongly related. Indeed, Service-oriented Architecture (SOA) has been considered as an implementation platform for business processes (BP) [4].

Traditional approaches to model the behavior of a service are based on activity-flows, with the data manipulated by these processes seen as second-class citizens. An example are transition systems that allow to describe the control flow, but they are not suited to represent a full-fledged database.

However, data highly impact process execution since many decisions in processes are data driven. Consider, for example, the case of a shipping company that exposes an on-line service which allows its user to request for the shipment of boxes. A request can be accepted if the volume and the weight requirements are fulfilled. It is necessary for this service to use a database for storing the shipping orders. Similar examples can be found in bank process payments, e-commerce and e-government sites and many other contexts.

²SM4All—Smart hoMes for All, is an FP7 project running from 1 September 2008 to 31 August 2011. Cf. <http://www.sm4all-project.eu>

Traditional process-centric models become insufficient since the role of data in process grew significantly. It became essential to model the data domain and data flow within the process. The holistic view of data and processes seen together promises to avoid the notorious discrepancy between data modeling and process modeling of more traditional approaches that consider these two aspects separately [16]. In particular, this separation precludes the development of data-aware automatic tools for formal verification.

In order to fully specify the behavior of a service is necessary to adopt models that can specify it in a holistic view, namely by formalizing both the control flow and how the actions manipulate the data, thus combining both aspects into a holistic unit.

As pointed out in [19], the database theory community has developed solutions to overcome the dichotomy between data and processes, by introducing a new class of formalisms called “*data-aware processes*”. We resort to these formalisms, in particular we base on the so called *Data-Centric Dynamic System*, to describe the behavior of the services. We refer to such services with the name “*data-aware services*” (or DAS) .

Data-Centric Dynamic Systems (DCDSs). (Relational) *Data-Centric Dynamic Systems (DCDSs)* are systems where both aspects, the process and the manipulated data, are considered equally important. DCDSs are constituted by:

- a *data layer*, that can be seen as a relational database which stores the relevant information to be manipulated by the system;
- a *process layer* which defines a set of invocable (atomic) actions and a process that characterizes the dynamic behavior of the system. The execution of the action may involve external services that introduce fresh data into the data layer.

An action of a DCDS is defined by a signature, made up of the name of the action and the sequence of *parameters* required, and of a set of specification of *effects* that define how the execution of the action affects the database. The execution of actions can be ideally divided into two steps: first, actions query the current state of the data layer, and then use the results of such queries, together with the data returned from the external services calls, to instantiate the new state of the data layer. The specification of the control-flow is provided by a flexible rule-based mechanism. Technically, the process is defined by a set of *Condition-Action* rules (CA-rules) which tells at any moment which actions can be executed with which parameters. Since the execution of actions may involve calls to external services, providing fresh data inserted into the system, DCDSs are, typically, *infinite-state*. Therefore, the formal verification of the properties of these systems is in general undecidable, but there exist notable cases where decidability is achieved. In [9] is investigated the verification for first order variants of μ -calculus supporting first-order quantification across states.

1.3 Goals and contributions of the thesis

Although an enormous interest is moving around the service oriented approach, several aspects related to service composition need to be investigated.

In the service representation, much more attention needs to be paid to data-management capabilities, thus, allowing the possibility of modeling even more realistic problems. As previously discussed, the presence of data makes services infinite-state and, in general, undecidable. It constitutes a great challenge in service composition and verification.

Research on data-aware business processes constitutes a good starting point for tackling the problem of *data-aware service composition*. In particular, the database theory community has developed several techniques addressing the foundations of data-aware process analysis [19].

The aim of this thesis is to define a formal framework for the characterization and theoretical investigation of the problem of data-aware service composition. In particular we will focus on the case of services that share a common data layer. In doing this, the achieved results introduce a set of novelties with respect to the service composition state-of-the-art:

- We suggest a formalism for service behavioral description, that is able to represent a variety of dynamics with the peculiarity of capturing the data-management capabilities of the process implemented by services.
- We characterize the problem of data-aware service composition (in presence of a shared data layer).
- We devise an approach to data-aware service composition that introduces the notion of *action delegation*. This aspect is concerned with finding among available services an action (or more actions possibly invoked concurrently) that executes a desired action specification.
- We provide a technique for computing service composition in the special case when both composite and component services share a common database.

The following sections will briefly introduce these aspects.

1.3.1 Describing Services

In order to describe the behavior of services, we resort to the formalisms developed in data-aware process analysis, in particular we have drawn inspiration from *Data-Centric Dynamic Systems*.

A *data-aware service (or DAS)* is a system formed by two interacting layers:

- the *data layer*, which stores the relevant information to be manipulated by the service. It can be seen as a relational database, *possibly shared* with other services.

The data-layer specification has to describe: which values can be stored in the database, which is the (relational) schema the data should follow

(typically a relational schema and a set of integrity constraints) and the initial database instance.

- The *action layer*, running on top of the data layer, describes the dynamic behavior of the service and the progression mechanism for the data layer.

It is defined by three main components:

- *actions* which are used to update the current state of the the data layer. They query the instance of the data layer, and use the answer, possibly together with the data introduced by external service calls, to instantiate the new state of the data layer. An action is defined by a signature, made up of the name of the action and the sequence of *parameters* required, and of a set of specification of *conditional effects* that define what it is required to hold once the execution of the action is terminated. Effects are divided into an *add list* (that specifies which tuples will be added during the execution) and a *delete list* (that specifies which tuples will be deleted during the execution). Every literal not mentioned in these lists remains unchanged, that is the *frame axiom* “*.and nothing else changes*” [17, 28] holds but it is not explicitly stated. The effect specification is slightly different from that given for DCDSs that states explicitly, on the basis of the current state of the data layer, which tuples form the next state. Of course, the two approaches have the same expressive power.
- *External services* introduce new values to the data layer and can be called during the execution of the actions. They may model an input of an external value by an employee, a decision of a human controller, a call to an external web service etc. How the result is actually computed is unknown to the service since it comes from an external entity.
- The (business) *process* which is essentially a nondeterministic program that uses actions as atomic activities. The process is specified by means of a finite-state transition system representing the sequences of atomic actions that the service can potentially perform and a set of Condition-Action Rules (CA-Rules) that tells, at any moment, which actions can be executed and with which parameters. These rules are expressed by a First-Order Logic open formula (a FO query) defined over the database relational schema. The expressive power of the CA-Rules mechanism could allow to specify transition systems (e.g. by storing the state of the service in an ad-hoc relation), but we choose to use both specifications for gaining advantage of the verification techniques developed for transition systems. In this way, the transition system expresses how the execution of an action affects the process state of the service while the action execution is guarded by CA-Rules that are concerned only with data (or static) aspects.

The state of the service can be defined by the state of the process (it can be seen

as a token flowing through the transition system) and the state of the data layer (current database instance). The latter component makes the service an infinite state system.

1.3.2 Problem characterization

This thesis focuses on data-aware service composition in the particular case that available services and the target service are defined on top of a common data layer.

Our framework is mainly composed by a *composition engine* and an *orchestrator*. Each of these components implements an algorithm that faces with a phase of the service composition problem.

The Figure 1.1a shows a composition synthesis scenario. The community (we refer to it with the name “Multi-DAS system”) is formed by n available services that access to the same data layer, i.e. they share both the data schema (relational schema, initial database instance) and the current database instance by accessing to the same database management system (DBMS). Even the target service is defined with respect to the data layer of the Multi-DAS system. As showed in the picture and discussed in the introduction to Service Composition, we remark that the target service is, just, a desired behavioral specification without a corresponding software artifact able to enact it. Instead, the available

services are existing software components that export their behavior by means of the DAS formalism. The composition engine takes as input these descriptions and the specification of the target service (also described as a DAS), and computes the composition synthesis that specifies how to invoke the existing services in order to realize the target service behavior. It is convenient to introduce, at this point, a formal definition of the the *state* of a Multi-DAS system which is the basis for developing the solution techniques. This *state* is composed by the process state of the available services and the current state of data layer (the current database instance).

The Figure 1.1b shows the scenario in the orchestration phase, this represents the actuation of the service composition schema. The user of the target service (or “Target Service Client”, as called in the picture) requests for the execution of an action provided by the service and available in its current state. This action may be invoked through an ad-hoc user interface, an example is the prototype of the Orchestrator in the SM4All project ³. The request is captured by the Orchestrator, that delegates the execution of the requested action to an available service. The invoked service performs a procedure that realizes the specification of the desired (target) action by, possibly, updating the current database instance and by evolving the process state of the services. The Orchestrator decides the service to delegate the requested action on the basis of the composition synthesis and the current state of the Multi-DAS system.

Although the available services are independent components, the execution of the database updates have to follow the scheduling imposed by the DBMS. For this reason, we model the Multi-DAS system so to execute only one action at a time, in other words, services cannot execute actions in a real concurrent environment. As previously stated, actions are atomic, so they can be viewed as atomic *Stored Procedures* invoked by services.

1.3.3 Key differences with respect to the Roman Model

From this rough formulation of the problem, we noticed some important differences with respect to the “Roman Model”. The Roman approach imposes a tight form of delegation, that is, every action of the target service must be delegated to exactly one action. The action of the target service (or *target action*) and the *delegate* action must have the same name. Differently, in our framework this matching is done on the basis of the specification of two actions. In this way, *our approach allows to delegate the execution of the target action to more than one action*. The delegate actions cooperate to realize the desired specification.

For instance, consider the case of an action *BookAndPay* that confirms a reservation for an accommodation and transfers to the bank account of the hotel the amount needed. The action *BookAndPay* might be delegated to an action *Book* and another action *Pay*. Each of these two actions accomplishes a particular sub-task of *BookAndPay*, or, conversely, *BookAndPay* can be viewed as a combination of the action *Book* and the action *Pay*. In this case, when

³Refer to <http://www.sm4all-project.eu/> for more details.

the user of the target service wants to execute the action *BookAndPay* the Orchestrator has to invoke, first the service that is able to perform *Book* and then the one that can perform *Pay*.

The example above presents a case of combination of two actions which are normally executed in sequence, i.e. first the reservation is confirmed then it is paid. Moreover, our framework allows to combine action that can be executed concurrently. An example can be an action *BookTheFlightAndBookTheAccommodation*. In this case the Orchestrator invokes concurrently the services designed to perform the actions.

As the previous examples highlights, it is possible to distinguish two types of compounded actions: those compliant with a concurrent invocation of their components and those with components that are to be invoked sequentially. Of course, depending on the execution model chosen, the Orchestrator complexity changes. In the first case, it invokes the execution of the desired procedures and wait their termination. In the latter case, the execution of an action involves more steps.

The action combination mechanism allows to extend the community capabilities by providing new actions that are derived from the exiting ones. These compounded actions have to operate as the atomic ones. The effect specification of a compounded action can be obtained by joining the effect specifications of its components (the actions of which it is composed).

Clearly, not all actions are suited for combination, some of them might arise congruency issues, e.g. consider two concurrent actions that update the same tuple, the effect of their execution might change due to the scheduling of the two actions. To be precise, we consider legal any compounded action that, for any scheduling of its components, the overall effect of its execution results as an execution of an atomic action.

In this thesis, *we provide a formal specification of compliance among actions and we devise a straightforward syntactic condition that is able to check it.*

In order to take advantage of the action combination mechanism for the service composition purpose, we need two preliminary steps:

1. We define the community capabilities (the set of actions, possibly compounded, that the community can perform) by combining the available actions in order to find new compounded ones. Actually, in this work we propose three settings for the community action set. The first set proposed is made up of the actions of the available system (individually taken as in the Roman Model). The other two proposals are constituted by compounded actions. In the second, action components are to be executed concurrently (the composition synthesis does not impose an execution sequence) and, in the third, in sequence (the execution sequence is imposed by the synthesis). From now on, we refer to the set of actions of the community by ignoring where these actions come from, i.e. by ignoring which of these three approaches is followed to build the set of community actions. The correspondence between community actions and available actions (actions of the available services) can be maintained by a mapping

for the use of the Orchestrator at the execution time.

2. For every community action, we define the conditions to be satisfied for allowing the action execution, that is, we characterize, by means of a formula, the state from which the action can be executed.

1.3.4 Solution techniques

In this section, we introduce the ideas constituting the basis of the techniques for computing the composition synthesis. Intuitively, the work of the composition engine can be ideally divided into two steps:

1. The engine calculates every possible *situation*. In this scenario, a situation can be defined by the state of the Multi-DAS system together with the state of the target system. Notice that these two elements share a common element, that is the state of the data layer.
2. For each possible situation, if the target service can perform⁴ an action α_t , then the composition engine has to check the existence of an action of the community α_c that can realize the specification of α_t , i.e. the two actions have the same effect specification.

We propose an approach that separates static (or data) aspects concerning the composition from the dynamic ones. The main focus of the static aspects is on evolving the data layer as the target DAS describes. Instead, the dynamic aspects focus only on executing conversations described by the transition system of target service. The Roman Model represents a valid method to face the latter issues. For these reasons, first, we focus only on the static aspects by considering a scenario where services allow any possible conversation (*stateless setting*); and then, by tacking advantage of the techniques developed for the stateless case and those proposed in the Roman approach, we address the case of constrained conversations (*stateful setting*).

Stateless setting. We started our analysis by considering the case of a community composed by n *stateless services*. We call stateless every service that, at any time, can execute any action (the execution of actions does not affect the process state of the service). The process for this class of services can be specified through a single-state transition system. In this setting, the execution of an action is guarded only by CA-Rules, so, only the data-layer instance is relevant for defining the state of the services (and of the Multi-DAS system). In this case, a composition exists when: *in every data-layer state, if the target service can execute an action α_t (with some arguments), then, the Multi-DAS system must be able to perform an action α_c that realizes the effect specification of α_t* . In order to realize the specification of α_t , α_c must be invoked with the same arguments passed to α_t .

⁴We say that a service of the Multi-DAS system can perform an action in a situation, when, both the process state and the data layer state allow to perform the action.

Indeed, in this case, the problem of checking the existence of a composition can be reduced to the problem of calculating the so-called *Action Delegation Relation* between the action set of the target service and the action set of the Multi-DAS system. An Action Delegation Relation is essentially a mapping from the former set to the latter set. We say that an action α_1 can be delegated to an action α_2 if:

- *the two actions have the same effect specification.* The two actions might be defined with respect to different parameters, so, a *translation* is needed to match the two specifications.

This is a syntactic condition which can be easily verified by analyzing the two specifications and by finding a suited parameter translation.

- *when α_1 can be executed with some arguments, it must be always possible to execute α_2 with arguments obtained by applying the parameter translation on the arguments of α_1 .*

This condition is more involving because it need a more sophisticated form of verification. First of all, in a stateless setting, an action α can be executed with some arguments, if these arguments satisfies the CA-Rule associated to α . Therefore, the above condition can be rephrased as follows: if the arguments of α_1 satisfy its CA-Rule, then the translation (suitably obtained) of these arguments must satisfy the CA-Rule associated to α_2 . This condition can be easily synthesized in a FO implication formula. The technique proposed in [9] can verify that, in every state achieved by the system (i.e. a state of the data layer), this implication holds. This method is necessary in the general case of a complete FOL formula, but there are simpler cases where the implication can be easily verified, e.g. when the implication can be expressed through a formula of the Propositional Logic, or, when the guards of the two actions are Conjunctive Queries.

In order to calculate every possible state, the verification method (of [9]) need to know which actions the system can execute. It is easy to note that, in this approach, the Multi-DAS system performs only the actions whose specification matches one of the target service. Hence, the states (of the data layer) achieved by the Multi-DAS system are only those described by the target service. Furthermore, this method requires that the target service to be data bounded, that is, the states of the data layer (infinite, in general) can be reduced to a finite number of representative instances.

In the stateless setting, the service composition schema is enacted by a very simple software component, called *Action-Delegator*. Given a target action, this component returns a set of delegate actions associated to it (through the Action-Delegation Relation). The Action-Delegator can be automatically generated from the Action-Delegation Relation. The schema does not require of a convoluted Orchestrator, it has to accomplish the tasks of capturing the target request, and, invoking an action designed by the Action-Delegator (Figure 1.2).

Stateful setting. In addition to the CA-Rules, in the stateful setting, the action execution is constrained by a transition system which specifies the sequences of atomic actions that a service can perform. Therefore, a situation is defined by the state of the Multi-DAS system (the process states of the community and the state of the shared data-layer) and the process state of the target service. Moreover, an additional transition system (which is called “Transition system of the community”) is needed to describe the overall behavior of the community. As proposed in the Roman model, this transition system is computed by means of the asynchronous product of the transition systems of the community services.

In this case, a composition exists when: *in every possible situation, if the target service can execute an action α_t (with some arguments), then the Multi-DAS system must be able to perform an action α_c that realizes the effect specification of α_t .* The difference between the stateless and stateful case is in the definition of *situation*, that, in the latter case, includes also the process state of the systems.

The verification of the composition condition involves two different problems. The first is the *Action Delegation Problem*, i.e. the problem of finding, for each target action, a community action that realizes (in every state of the data layer) its specification. Since every conversation with a stateful service can be mimed by the stateless service derived to it⁵, we noticed that the technique developed for the stateless case can be applied in the stateful case. Once the Action Delegation Relation is computed, to every action of the target service it is associated (at least) an action of the community that can execute its specification (in every data-layer state achieved by the Multi-DAS system). But, differently from the stateless case, this delegation can be accomplished only if the Multi-DAS system is in a process state that allows to execute the delegate action.

Indeed, this issue is matter of the *Behavioral Composition Problem*. This problem is concerned with checking that, in every possible situation of the systems process-states, every available⁶ target action has an available community action-delegate. In order to tackle this issue, we recur to the same approach showed in the Roman Model which is based on the notion of simulation. We recall that, given two transition systems S and S' , S simulates S' if, intuitively, every (possibly infinite) path⁷ of S' is also a path of S . Therefore, if the transition system of the community simulates the transition system of the target service, then the community is able to realize all possible target conversations. The difference between the two approaches is the method for matching the transitions. In the Roman Model two transitions match when they have the same name, instead, in our approach the target action matches only with actions associated to it through the Action-Delegation Relation.

It is worth noting that these two problems identify two separate aspects of the Service Composition. The Action-Delegation problem involves a sort of *static aspects*⁸. They are concerned with finding the actions that update the database as the target service describes, and it is ignored where the chosen actions lead

⁵The stateless service is obtained by reducing the transition system in a single state.

⁶The action can be executed in the actual state of the service.

⁷To be precise, a path rooted in the initial state of the transition system.

⁸They can be specified with local conditions only.

Figure 1.2: Orchestrator scenario in details

to. Whereas, the Behavioral Composition involves a variety of dynamic aspects⁹ that are concerned with finding suitable actions leading to states where it is (still) possible delegate (to the community) the execution of actions of the target service.

In the stateful setting, the enactment of the Service Composition schema, showed in Figure 1.2, requires a slightly more complicated Orchestrator respect to the previous case. The Orchestrator has to monitor the process state of the Multi-DAS system and, then, invoke delegate actions that are compliant with it. In the Figure 1.2 we show the interplay of the various components at the execution time. According to its current state, the target service proposes to the client a set of available actions; the client selects one of such actions (step 1); the request for the selected action is forwarded to the Orchestrator (step 2); the Orchestrator get from the Action Delegator the delegate-actions for the requested action (step 3 and 4); finally, the Orchestrator invokes the execution of a delegate-action according to the current state of the Multi-DAS system (step 5).

1.4 Thesis Structure

The rest of this thesis is structured as follows:

- In Chapter 2, we present the achievements in Service Composition and in Data-Aware Process Modeling on which our work is based upon.
- In Chapter 3, we introduce the data-aware services (DASs) constituting the fundamental building block of our framework.

⁹They can be specified with local and non-local conditions.

- In Chapter 4, we present the elements constituting the core of our framework, we provide the definition of the problem of composing a finite set of data-aware services (DAS) so to devise a new composite DAS. We define the Multi-DAS System, a component that allow us to describe, in terms of DAS language, the overall behavior of a community of available DASs that share a common data layer.
- In Chapter 5, we propose a technique for extending the Multi-DAS system capabilities by providing new actions that are derived from the exiting ones.
- In Chapter 6, we provide the solution techniques for computing a data-aware service composition in the case of a common data-layer shared by the available services and the target service.
- Finally, in Chapter 7 we summarize our work and we discuss the future research directions.

Chapter 2

Background

2.1 Services

*Services*¹ (or Web Services, or e-Services as often referred to in the literature) are software systems offered by service providers in order to be composed and reused in a distributed, web-based environment. They are self-contained, modular applications that can be described, published, located and dynamically invoked, in a programming language independent way [15]. Services perform functions (also called actions), which can be anything from simple requests to complicated procedures, e.g. submitting an on-line application for a bank account or modifying an airline ticket order. They allow to expose over the Internet (or intra-net) the core competencies of an organization by using standard languages and protocols. Services are characterized by constraints on the possible sequences of actions they can perform, that are called *conversations*. An example of conversation is represented by the procedure for booking a flight, an airline ticket order can be confirmed only if the user has sent the flight details.

Services are offered by service providers that procure the service implementations, supply the service descriptions, and provide related technical support. Since services may be offered by different enterprises and communicate over a web-based environment, they need of a distributed computing infrastructure for both intra- and cross-enterprise. Clients of services can be human or other applications within or outside the enterprise. According to [30], in order to satisfy these requirements services should be:

1. *Technology neutral*, i.e. they should be invocable through standardized technologies available to almost all environments.
2. *Loosely coupled*, i.e. they should not require knowledge or any internal structures or conventions (context) at the client or service side.

¹With the generic term “*Service*” we refer to any application component accessible in a programmatic way, Web Services are the most common examples.

3. *Support location transparency*, i.e. the definition of the services should be stored in a repository. These repositories should be accessible by a variety of clients that can locate and invoke the services irrespective from their location.

Services come in two flavors: *simple* and *composite* services. Composite services assembles existing services that access to information and combine functions from possibly several service providers.

2.1.1 Web Services

The World Wide Web consortium (W3C) provided an accurate definition of Web service [8].

“A Web service is a software system identified by a URI, whose public interfaces and bindings are defined and described using XML. Its definition can be discovered by other software systems. These systems may then interact with the Web service in a manner prescribed by its definition, using XML based messages conveyed by Internet protocols.”

One of the first issues to be addressed by a technology supporting this definition is the service description. This task involves several problems:

- *Common base language*: a meta-language is needed as basis form specifying all the languages necessary to describe the aspects related to services. XML is used for this purpose and the Simple Object Access Protocol (SOAP) [2] is used to allow the exchanging of information among the web services.
- *Interface description languages (IDLs)*: are needed to generate (possibly, automatically) stubs. They have to specify the functionality of the service, the interaction modes and the service address. Technically, the interface is the description of the signatures of a set of operations that are available for invocation. The dominant proposal is the Web Services Description Language (WSDL) [?].
- *Business Protocols*: the set of rules specifying the conversations supported by the service. To this end, some examples are Web Service Conversation Language (WSCL) [10] and Business Process Execution Language (BPEL) [6].
- *Additional Properties*: this may include non-functional properties such as textual description. This information can be attached using the Universal Description, Discovery and Integration (UDDI) [11].

Semantic Web Service. *Semantic Web* techniques consist of applying knowledge representation techniques in the Internet environment so to provide richer descriptions of Web resources. The aim is to convert the actual web, dominated by un- or semi-structured documents, into a “Web of data”. *Semantic Web*

Service is defined as the augmentation of the Web Services descriptions through Semantic Web annotations, in order to facilitate their discovery, composition, invocation and monitoring. For this purpose are proposed DAML-S/OWL-S [7, 1]. In particular OWL-S describe web services, in terms of their inputs, outputs, preconditions and (possibly conditional) effects, and their process model. Furthermore, it allows to capture the notion of world state as a set of fluents.

2.1.2 Service Oriented Computing and Architectures (SOC and SOA)

While the services encapsulate the business functionality, some form of inter-service infrastructure is required to facilitate service interactions and communication. *Service-Oriented Computing* (SOC) is the computing paradigm whose basic elements are services, used as building blocks to devise other services [30]. Service-Oriented Computing aims at building a world of collaborating services that are being loosely coupled to flexibly create dynamic business processes and agile applications, distributed within and across organizational boundaries and computing platforms. *Service-Oriented Architectures* (SOAs) are developed for realizing the SOC purpose, mainly consist of a middleware that enables the discovery, utilization, and integration of services. SOC/SOA aim to separate software engineering from programming, to emphasize on software engineering, and to deemphasize on programming. In this scenario, we can identify three basic roles:

- *Service providers* that use a programming language to build program components, all of these wrapped with open standard interfaces;
- *Service brokers* that allow services to be registered and published for public access;
- *Application builders* (or *Service Aggregators* as sometimes called in the literature to emphasize their mission) no longer create software from scratch using basic programming language constructs; instead they specify the application logic in a high-level workflow specification language, using standard services as components. They are organizations that compose multiple services into a new, single composite service offering.

The Figure 2.1 shows a general scenario in the Service Oriented paradigm. The accumulation of available services over time will make it possible to find almost any desired component services. Thus, the job market demand is shifting towards high-level composition modeling skills for application building through composition of reusable services [35].

SOA allows to provide services to either end-user applications or other services distributed in a network through published and discoverable interfaces. The basic SOA defines an interaction between software agents as an exchange of messages between service requesters (clients) and service providers. The service provider defines a service description of the service and publishes it thanks to

Figure 2.1: The picture shows a general scenario in the Service Oriented paradigm.

service brokers. The service requestor uses a find operation to retrieve the service description typically from a service broker, i.e. a repository like UDDI, and uses the service description to bind with the service provider and invoke the service or interact with service implementation. The Figure 2.2 summarizes the interplay among the various actors in a SOA.

2.2 Service Composition

The widely adopted approach is to code composite services (such as mashups, that uses contents from many sources) by means of conventional programming languages that bridge heterogeneous applications. Instead, in the service oriented approach, a service can be interpreted as a procedure (or method) in programming languages, therefore, a set of services as a sort of programming library. This similarity is the basis of the service composition problem: as exactly as in a programming language procedures/methods are combined to produce more complex procedures/methods, so services can be combined to build more complex services.

Service Composition is the problem of automatically combining a set of available services (often called community of available services) all exporting their behavior, so to synthesize a more complex service, according to a desired description (called target service or simply target).

The problem concerns with realizing a (virtual) target service, described by means of an high-level language (no longer coded in a programming language), by resorting to (existing) available services. In other words, the fragments of

Figure 2.2: The picture shows the interplay among the various actors in a SOA.

the target service computation are to be suitably delegated to available services. Service composition problem involves two different issues:

1. *Composition synthesis* (or simply composition) is concerned with synthesizing a new composite service, thus producing a specification on how coordinate available services to obtain the target service, i.e. for each possible situation (calculated on the basis of possible user choices) the synthesis specifies which available service must be invoked to execute a desired action of the target service. The synthesis can be obtained either *automatically*, i.e. using a tool that implements a composition algorithm, or manually by a human that calculates all the cases.
2. *Orchestration* is concerned with coordinating available services (by monitoring control and data flow among them) in order to guarantee the correct execution of the composite service (synthesized in the composition phase).

A number of approaches have been proposed to tackle the service composition problem. Most of them are inspired by the researches in cross-enterprise workflow and AI planning [32].

Orchestration has been widely addressed by other research areas, and most of the work on service orchestration is based on research in workflows.

To support this purpose *Web service composition middleware* are needed for providing abstractions and infrastructures facilitating the definition and the execution of target (also called composite) service. In doing so, the developers can focus only on the business logic. According to [5], a Web service composition middleware includes:

- A *composition model and language* enabling the specification of the services to be combined, and, the order and the way in which the different services are to be invoked.
- A *run-time environment* that executes the business logic of the composite service by invoking component services as defined in the schema.

2.3 The “Roman” Model

One of the most significant and influent [26] approaches to service composition is the so-called “*Roman Model*”, in which service behaviors are abstracted as transition systems [14, 12, 31, 15, 22]. This proposal focuses on an abstract notion of activities (without modeling how their execution impacts the world), and model services as finite state automaton with transitions labeled by these activities (also called actions). The main features of this model are summarized as follows:

- The available services are grouped together in the so-called *community*. Each service belonging to this community exports its conversational behavior described as a nondeterministic transition system. The overall behavior of the entire community is also specified by means of transition systems.
- The available services in the community share a common action set. An action denotes an interaction between service and clients and may involve other aspects, not necessarily modeled in the description, such as the acquirement of new information.
- The model introduces a simple form of data-awareness that allows to represent finite-state data structures (e.g. a set of variables that range over a finite set of values) shared among the services. Precisely, in addition to available services, a community contains a so-called finite-state *data box* (also called environment), i.e. an additional nondeterministic transition system modeling the evolution of a shared data structure whose state is affected by the execution of the activities of the available services. Here, the nondeterminism is used to model the partial predictability. The data box can capture situations where services deal with data over finite domain. The state of the environment is assumed fully observable by all services, including the target.
- The behavior of each available service is described in terms of a finite state transition system, i.e. Kripke structures whose transitions are labeled only by shared actions. To be precise, in order to model the partial controllability, the transition system describing an available service is *nondeterministic*. A typical interaction-step client-service follows these steps: the service offers a set of executable actions, the chooses one of these and the service executes it. This means that the execution of an action leads to a state of a finite set. The actions executions may affect the environment, hence they are equipped with preconditions that check the state of the environment and postconditions that describe the effects of the execution on the environment.
- The target is described as a finite-state, *deterministic* transition system that uses actions of the community. Determinism here captures the absence of uncertainty over the desired behavior, i.e. given a state and a action

we know exactly the next behavior state, while this is not the case for nondeterministic behaviors.

- The orchestrator has the ability of scheduling services on a step-by-step basis. It is a component that can instruct the available services to execute an action among those allowed in their current state. The orchestrator has full-observability on the community and the environment.

In this approach, the composition synthesis task consists in synthesizing an orchestrator able to coordinate the community services so to mimic the behavior of the target service. The target service is realized by suitably delegating the action requested by the client of the target service to one of the available service.

The framework proposes a sound and complete composition algorithm that takes as input a set of descriptions of existing services, and a desired behavior (or “target” behavior) and provides as output a composition synthesis. Specifically, the composition problem has been tackled with different techniques, starting by exploiting a reduction to satisfiability of a Propositional Dynamic Logic (PDL) [24] formula. Then, in [31] was proposed the algorithm based on the notion of simulation [25]. Intuitively, the existing services “simulate” the target service if, whenever the target is able to execute an activity, there always exists an available service that can execute that activity. Moreover, the framework proposes an algorithm that synthesizes an orchestrator program from the simulation relation between the overall behavior of the available services and the target service.

It is proved that the existence of compositions can be checked in polynomial time in the size (number of states) of the available behaviors and of the target behavior, and in exponential time in the number of available behaviors.

A concrete case of application of automated service composition with the Roman Model has been performed in the SM4All² EU research project, recently and successfully concluded [22].

The Roman Model was further extended by the COLOMBO framework [13] by introducing messages and data types. In details, the fundamental aspects in COLOMBO are: the *world state* that can be viewed as a database instance over a relational database schema, the *atomic processes* (provided by the services) that can access, modify the world state by means of conditional effects, and *messages* exchange among the services. In COLOMBO services are described as transition systems able to execute operations with input/output parameters, and their execution updates the underlying database. Moreover the database affects the action execution through preconditions. On top of this, they have defined a notion of data-aware simulation that, in addition to the usual simulation, it takes into account both input/output parameters and the underlying database. The decidability of the composition is achieved under very tight assumptions (i.e. COLOMBO^{k,b}) that bounds the database. In doing so, the possible instances (infinite, in general) of the data layer can be reduced to a finite set of representatives.

²SM4All—Smart hoMes for All, is an FP7 project running from 1 September 2008 to 31 August 2011. Cf. <http://www.sm4all-project.eu>

2.4 Business Process Management (BPM)

A Business Process is defined as a collection of inter-related events, activities (or tasks) that collectively realize a business objective by (possibly) involving several actors and objects. A business process can be viewed as a sequence of activities interleaved with decision points. In [23], Dumas et al. captured the Business Process Management (BPM) in a nutshell as:

“a body of methods, techniques and tools to discover, analyze and redesign, execute and monitor business processes.”

The definition highlights the fact that BPM is involved in different phases of the business process lifecycle. Organizations identified in the BPM the ability of optimizing the business processes thus to improve their productivity.

The most important BPM aspect, for the purpose of this thesis, is the modeling phase. In fact, we borrow from this research area the techniques for describing the behavior of the services. Most of the current approaches to process modeling are *activity-centric*, they are based on an explicit specification of the activities to be performed and the execution relationships among them, by disregarding the data that the processes manipulates. Examples of this approach are Business Process Modeling Notation (BPMN) [18] and Yet Another Workflow Language (YAWL) [36]. In such languages the main focus is on the control flow of the processes, and, the only relationship with data is confined in the definition of a set of information objects flowing through the activities as input/output parameters. These approaches are not suited to represent the processes in which the execution is affected by (or affects) a full-fledged database.

However, data highly impact process execution since many decisions in processes are data driven. Consider, for example, the case of a shipping company that exposes an on-line service which allows its user to request for the shipment of boxes. A request can be accepted if the volume and the weight requirements are fulfilled. It is necessary for this service to use a database for storing the shipping orders. Similar examples can be found in bank process payments, e-commerce and e-government sites and many other contexts.

Traditional process-centric models become insufficient since the role of data in process grew significantly. It became essential to model the data domain and data flow within the process. The holistic view of data and processes seen together promises to avoid the notorious discrepancy between data modeling and process modeling of more traditional approaches that consider these two aspects separately [16]. In particular, this separation precludes the development of data-aware automatic tools for formal verification.

In the last years, the *data-centric* approach has been proposed to overcome the lacks of the process-centric models. In these proposals data are treated as a first-class citizens by formally defining which are the data manipulated by the process and how these data affect the process execution. As pointed out in [19], the database theory community has developed solutions to overcome the dichotomy between data and processes, by introducing a new class of formalisms called “*data-aware processes*”. In data-aware business processes activities and

data manipulated by them are considered equally important. We resort to these formalisms, in particular we base on the so called *Data-Centric Dynamic System*, to describe the behavior of the services.

In conclusion, we want to emphasize the relationship between BPM and SOC/SOA. In fact, the research areas on BPM and SOC/SOA are strongly related, Service Oriented Architectures (SOAs) are widely considered as an implementation platform for business processes (BP) [4]. The jointed investigation of BPM and SOA together is expected to result in several benefits for both areas. In particular, BPM can be used to enrich the poor service description by creating and specifying its operations, and, by determining the relations among them (i.e. data and control flow). This approach helps in several challenges of the Service-Oriented Computing, such as service discovery.

2.5 Data-Centric Dynamic Systems (DCDSs)

We base the description of the DCDS formalism as proposed in [9]. (Relational) *Data-Centric Dynamic Systems (DCDSs)* are systems where both aspects, the process and the manipulated data, are considered equally important. DCDSs are constituted by:

- a *data layer*, that can be seen as a relational database which stores the relevant information to be manipulated by the system;
- a *process layer* which defines a set of invocable (atomic) actions and a process that characterizes the dynamic behavior of the system. The execution of the action may involve external services that introduce fresh data into the data layer.

An action of a DCDS is defined by a signature, made up of the name of the action and the sequence of *parameters* required, and of a set of specification of *effects* that define how the execution of the action affects the database. The definition of the action effects is inspired to tuple generating dependencies (TGDs)[3], except that the negation when querying the database is allowed to capture “if-then-else” style business rules.

The execution of actions can be ideally divided into two steps: first, actions query the current state of the data layer, and then use the results of such queries, together with the data returned from the external services calls, to instantiate the new state of the data layer. The external services behave deterministically, i.e. the result of the call depends only on passed parameters, or non-deterministically, i.e. two calls of an external service with the same arguments may return distinct results during the same run.

The specification of the control-flow is provided by a flexible rule-based mechanism. Technically, the process is defined by a set of *Condition-Action* rules (CA-rules) which tells at any moment which actions can be executed with which parameters. These rules are expressed by a First-Order Logic open formula (a FO query) over the database schema.

Since the execution of actions may involve calls to external services, providing fresh data inserted into the system, DCDSs are, typically, *infinite-state*. Therefore, the formal verification of the properties of these systems is in general undecidable, but there exist notable cases where decidability is achieved. In [9] is investigated the verification for first order variants of μ -calculus supporting first-order quantification across states. If the external services behave deterministically, it is showed that the decidability of the verification is achieved under the assumption that the fresh data introduced along a run are bounded (the property to be verified must be expressed in a μ -calculus variant that preserves knowledge of objects appeared along a run). If the external services expose a non-deterministic behavior, it is showed that decidability of the verification is achieved under the assumption that there exist a bound on the number of distinct values simultaneously present in the database (the property to be verified must be expressed in a μ -calculus that preserve the knowledge of objects only if they are continuously present).

According to [19], DCDSs are gaining momentum due to their *expressiveness* that guarantees the ability of capture a wide range of concrete systems, and, the decidability of their *verification* formalism that provides the ability to capture both linear-time and branching-time properties.

Chapter 3

Data-Aware Services

In this chapter, we introduce the data-aware services (DASs) constituting the fundamental building block of our framework. This formalism allows to describe the service behavior in terms of the actions they can perform, by paying more attention (with respect to the previous proposals) on the data involved in the service execution. Furthermore, we define a semantics in terms of possibly infinite transition systems. Finally, we propose an approach for checking whether the achievable data-layer states satisfy a property expressed in first-order logic.

3.1 Basics on Data-Aware Services

Generally speaking, a *data-aware service* is a software system that interacts with its clients in order to achieve a specific goal. The clients of a service can be either a human, or another service. Intuitively, a data-aware service represents the typical scenario of a program that manipulates data during its execution. In this scenario we can identify the data layer (that can be viewed as a relational database); and, the business layer (the software intended to interact with client and to update the database, called *action layer* in DAS terminology). Data-aware services are characterized by the data schema they work on and by their conversational behavior, i.e. possible sequences of actions they can perform.

Following [12], we identify the aspects characterizing a data-aware service as:

- The *schema* (in terms of functional requirements) is specified by the process implemented by the service together with the data schema it requires;
- The *implementation and deployment* that indicate *how* the service is realized, in terms of software applications and database systems corresponding to the service schema;
- The service *instance* is an occurrence of the service effectively running and interacting with a client. In general, several running instances (of the same service) may *co-exist*, each one executing independently from the others

and managing its own database instance (which is independent from other instances of the same service).

Typically, the interaction client-service is realized by the following steps:

1. The *client activates* an instance of the deployed service;
2. The *service proposes* to the client a set of actions it can perform in its current state;
3. The *client chooses* one of such action, and he¹ *provides* (if any) the input parameters that the action may require, and then, he *waits* for the fulfillment of the specific task;
4. The *service executes* the client selection by *updating* the database according to the chosen action and by *moving* to a new state;
5. The interaction is either “*stopped*”, if the service is in a final state, or, *continued* by returning to the step 2.

We assume that the client get the results of the service operations by querying the database and, therefore, the modeled actions do not define any return statements because it is superseded by the effect specification. In order to gather the results of its operations, we assume that the client can arbitrarily query the database, at any time, without invoking any action. In this way, we focus only on aspects that influence the service execution, i.e. database updates, by ignoring those related with user interaction, i.e. modeling results consumed by an user.

3.2 Data-aware services (DASs)

In order to describe the behavior of services, we need of a formalism that, on the one hand, is able to represent a variety of dynamics with the peculiarity of capturing the data-management capabilities of the process implemented by services, and, on the other hand, allows the verification of sophisticated properties. These aspects are, mainly, embodied by DCDS [9] which forms the foundation of the formalism that we are going to introduce, called DAS (Data-aware service). Such model allows to capture both the dynamic capabilities of services and how its execution affects a (or, is affected by) a full-fledged database. Furthermore, this formalism gives the possibility of describing a wide range of real scenarios.

A *data-aware service (or DAS)* is a pair $\mathcal{S} = \langle \mathcal{D}, \mathcal{P} \rangle$ where the components represent two interacting layers:

- The *data layer*, denoted with \mathcal{D} , which stores the relevant information to be manipulated by the service. It can be seen as a relational database, *possibly shared* with other services.

¹In what follows, we refer to the client with the “he” pronoun.

- The *action layer*, denoted with \mathcal{P} , running on top of the data layer, describes the dynamic behavior of the service and the progression mechanism for the data layer. It is formed by invocable (atomic) actions and a process based on them. Executing an action has effects on the data manipulated by the system, on the process state, and, on the information exchanged with the external world (i.e. external service calls).

Despite the expressive power of the DCDS can model a wide variety of business processes, we choose to equip DCDS with a finite-state transition system for describing the dynamic behavior of the service. This choice allows us to gain advantage of the verification techniques developed for transition systems. In this way, the transition system expresses how the execution of an action affects the process state of the service, while, the action execution is guarded by a DCDS-like rule formalism that are concerned only with data aspects.

3.2.1 DAS Data layer

Intuitively, the data layer keeps all the information of interest for the service application. For the definition of the data layer, we rely on that given for DCDSs (cf. [9]). The data layer is constituted by a relational schema \mathcal{R} equipped with a set of equality constraints \mathcal{E} , and, by an initial database instance \mathcal{I}_0 that is compliant with the relational schema, and, that satisfies the constraints. The values that can be stored in the database belong to a countably infinite domain \mathcal{C} . The elements of \mathcal{C} are treated as constants, and we interchangeably use the terms constants and values. We assume that, at any time, the current instance of the data layer can be arbitrarily queried, and can be updated through action execution.

Given a database instance \mathcal{I} , it is defined its **active domain**, denoted by $\text{ADOM}(\mathcal{I})$, as the subset \mathcal{C} such that $c \in \text{ADOM}(\mathcal{I})$ if and only if c occurs in \mathcal{I} .

Formally, a data layer is a tuple $\mathcal{D} = \langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle$ where:

- \mathcal{C} is the countably infinite domain of the values accepted in the database;
- $\mathcal{R} = \{\mathcal{R}_1, \dots, \mathcal{R}_n\}$ is the database schema, made up of a finite set of relational schemas;
- $\mathcal{E} = \{\mathcal{E}_1, \dots, \mathcal{E}_n\}$ is a finite set of equality constraints, e.g. they can be used to state keys of relations or other forms of integrity constraints. Each equality constraint \mathcal{E}_i has the form $Q_i(\vec{x}) \rightarrow \bigwedge_{j=1..k} z_{ij} = y_{ij}$, where Q_i is a domain independent first-order query defined over the relational schema \mathcal{R} (possibly using constants from $\text{ADOM}(\mathcal{I}_0)$), whose free variables are \vec{x} , and, z_{ij} and y_{ij} are either variables in \vec{x} or constants of $\text{ADOM}(\mathcal{I}_0)$;
- \mathcal{I}_0 is the database instance that represents the initial state of the data layer when the service instance is activated. \mathcal{I}_0 is consistent with \mathcal{R} and *satisfies* the constraints \mathcal{E} .

The relational schema \mathcal{R} and the set of equality constraints \mathcal{E} have to be satisfied in each state of the data layer, and therefore, it is forbidden to perform an action that would lead to a data-layer state that violates either \mathcal{R} or \mathcal{E} .

3.2.2 DAS Action Layer

The *action layer*, denoted with \mathcal{P} , running on top of the data layer, describes, on the one hand, the progression mechanism for the data layer, i.e. it defines how the execution of the actions evolves a state of the data layer to a new one; and, on the other hand, the dynamic behavior of the service, e.g. the sequences of operations allowed by the service. The former purpose is accomplished by a finite-set of actions \mathcal{A} , that are used to evolve the current state of the data layer into a new one. The actions query the current instance of the data layer, and use the answer, possibly together with the data introduced by external service calls (defined by the set \mathcal{F}), to instantiate the new state of the data layer. The external services are an artifice for introducing fresh values into the data layer. The latter purpose is accomplished by a finite-state *transition system* (defined by $\mathbb{S}, s_0, \delta, \mathbb{F}$), whose transitions are labeled by service action, and, a finite set ϱ of so-called *Condition-Action Rules* (CA-Rules) that tells, at any moment, which actions can be executed with which parameters. These components define the (business) *process* implemented by the service which is, essentially, a nondeterministic program that uses actions as atomic activities.

Formally, an action layer \mathcal{P} , defined over the data layer $\mathcal{D} = \langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle$, is a tuple $\mathcal{P} = \langle \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{A}, \varrho, \mathbb{S}, s_0, \delta, \mathbb{F} \rangle$ where:

- \mathcal{F} is a finite set of functions, each representing an interface to an *external service*. Such functions can be called during the action execution, and as a result they produce a fresh value. They may model an input of an external value by an employee, a decision of a human controller, a call to an external web service etc. How the result is actually computed is unknown to the service since it comes from an external entity.
- \mathcal{A} is a finite set of *actions*, whose execution updates the data layer and evolves the process state of the service.
- ϱ is a finite set of *condition-action rules*, that are associated to actions and guard the arguments of their execution.
- \mathbb{S} is a finite set of *process states* of the service.
- $s_0 \in \mathbb{S}$ is the initial process state of the service.
- $\delta \subseteq \mathbb{S} \times \mathcal{A} \times \mathbb{S}$ is the transition relation among service process-states.
- $\mathbb{F} \subseteq \mathbb{S}$ is the set of the final process-states of the service.

In order to avoid confusions we distinct the *data-layer state* which is the actual state of the database, the *process state* which is the actual progress of the service in the transition system (it can be viewed as a token flowing through the

transition system), and, finally, the *state of the service* which is constituted by the previous components.

Actions. An action represents the formal specification of an atomic procedure (or method, or function) implemented by the service. It describes how the execution of the procedure affects the data layer by ignoring aspects that are irrelevant with respect to the composition task, e.g. the procedure notifies, by opening a new window, the success of a bank transaction. With a slight abuse of terminology, sometimes we will treat the action specification as invocable (and executable) as the procedure it represents.

Formally, an action $\alpha \in \mathcal{A}$ is an expression $\alpha(p_1, \dots, p_n) : \{e_1, \dots, e_m\}$ where:

- $\alpha(p_1, \dots, p_n)$ is the signature which is made up of the name of the action α and a sequence of *parameters* p_1, \dots, p_n , to be substituted with values when the action is invoked;
- $\{e_1, \dots, e_m\}$, also denoted with $\text{EFFECTS}(\alpha)$, is a set of specifications of *conditional effects*, that are required to hold once the execution of the action is terminated. The effect specification language will be introduced in the following Paragraph.

Effects. The effect specification defines which is *added to/deleted from* the current² instance of the database. Intuitively, the effect specification defines, by means of queries, which tuples currently stored in the database are involved in the action execution. The values stored in the selected tuples can be used to instantiate new tuples and/or as arguments for external service calls. Moreover, a selected tuple can be possibly deleted. Precisely, each effect defines an *add list* (that specifies which tuples will be added during the execution) and a *delete list* (that specifies which tuples will be deleted during the execution). Each list is formed by literals of \mathcal{R} . We assume that, every literal not mentioned in these lists remains unchanged, that is, the *frame axiom* “..and nothing else changes” [17, 28] holds but it is not explicitly stated. The effect specification is slightly different from that given for DCDSs that states explicitly, on the basis of the current state of the data layer, which tuples form the next state. Of course, the two approaches have the same expressive power. Our approach for specifying the conditional effect of an action is inspired to PDDL (Planning Domain Definition Language) [29].

Formally, each $e_i \in \text{EFFECTS}(\alpha)$ has the following structure:

$$q_i^+(\vec{x}) \wedge Q_i^- \rightsquigarrow \{\text{addlist}_i, \text{dellist}_i\}$$

where:

- $q_i^+(\vec{x}) \wedge Q_i^-$ is a query over \mathcal{R} whose terms are variables, action parameters, and constants from $\text{ADOM}(\mathcal{I}_0)$. The query can be split into q_i^+ which is an union of conjunctive queries, and Q_i^- which is an arbitrary First Order

²With “current” we intend the instance on which the action is executed.

DCDS	DAS
$\alpha(p_1) : \{$ $\quad P(x) \rightsquigarrow \{Q(x, const, f(p_1))\}$ $\quad R(x, y) \rightsquigarrow \{R(x, y)\}$ $\quad P(x) \rightsquigarrow \{P(x)\}$ $\}$	$\alpha(p_1) : \{$ $\quad P(x) \rightsquigarrow \{Q(x, const, f(p_1))\}$ $\quad Q(x, y, z) \rightsquigarrow \{\text{not } Q(x, y, z)\}$ $\}$

Table 3.1: Comparison of the action-specification languages

formula whose free variables are among those of q_i^+ . Intuitively, q_i^+ extracts a set of tuples from the current database instance and Q_i^- filters away some of them.

- *addlist_i* is the add list; it is specified by means a set of literals of \mathcal{R} . Each literal can includes: terms in $\text{ADOM}(\mathcal{I}_0)$, free variables in q_i^+ and Q_i^- , action parameters, and *Skolem* [33] terms formed by applying a function $f \in \mathcal{F}$ to one of the previous kinds of terms. Such Skolem terms represent external service calls and they are interpreted as the returned value chosen by an external entity when executing the action.
- *dellist_i* is the delete list; it is specified by means of a set of literals of \mathcal{R} . Each literal can include: terms in $\text{ADOM}(\mathcal{I}_0)$, free variables in q_i^+ and Q_i^- , and action parameters.

In what follows the literals of the two lists are presented in a unique list with the literals belonging to the delete list preceded by the keyword *not*.

Intuitively, when an action α is invoked all of its effects e_i are executed by: selecting the set of tuples that satisfy $q_i^+(\vec{x}) \wedge Q_i^-$; then, instantiating the literals of the two lists (the variables are substituted with the corresponding values that the query returns); and finally, updating the database by removing from the current state the proposition in *dellist_i* and adding those in *addlist_i*. Deletions are performed first, at once.

Example 3.2.1. In this example we compare the DAS language for the action specification with that proposed for DCDSs. Consider an action α is exported by a DAS and a DCDS. Suppose that the data layer of the two systems have the same relational schema $\mathcal{R} = \{R \setminus 2, P \setminus 1, Q \setminus 3\}$. Assume that the execution of the action α (over the current instance \mathcal{I}) causes the insertion of one tuple of Q for each tuple stored in P (currently in \mathcal{I}); an added tuple is constituted by the value of the corresponding P -tuple, the constant *const* and the value returned by invoking the external service f with the action parameter p_1 . Moreover, α deletes the tuple previously contained in Q . P and R are not updated.

The Table 3.1 compares the action specification languages of DCDS and DAS. The effect, $P(x) \rightsquigarrow \{Q(x, const, f(p_1))\}$, that causes the insertions in Q , it is expressed in the same way in both languages. The specification of the DCDS has to explicitly specify which tuples of the current state forms the next state,

Figure 3.1: The transition system representing all possible conversations of a login service.

therefore, α has to include the effects $R(x,y) \rightsquigarrow \{R(x,y)\}$ and $P(x) \rightsquigarrow \{P(x)\}$ for specifying that R and P remains unchanged. These two statements are not needed in the DAS language. Conversely from DCDS, in DAS we need the effect $Q(x,y,z) \rightsquigarrow \{\text{not } Q(x,y,z)\}$ for specifying that the Q -tuple of \mathcal{I} do not form the next database state.

■

Process. The (business) process defines a nondeterministic program that uses actions as atomic activities. It is described by means of a *transition system* that specifies the possible conversations (i.e. a sequence of actions) allowed by the system and a set of *Condition-Action Rules* that guards the parameters used for invoking the action execution.

The transition systems (or TS) are Kripke structures [20] whose transitions are labeled by service actions. We assume that each legal path (rooted in the initial state) through the transitions corresponds to a conversation supported by the service.

Example 3.2.2. Consider a *login* service that, on the one hand, protects the access to some resources (e.g. a server or any kind of resources that do not affect the service execution), and, on the other hand, allows a human-monitored form of registration for new users. A possible transition system for this service is presented in the Figure 3.1. The service starts by proposing the choice between requesting the registration of a new user or logging a registered one. If the user asks for a registration, then, depending on the service decision about the request acceptance, he can activate the account or retry with a new registration. Otherwise, a registered user can log him into the system, then, he takes advantage of his status (for instance, by accessing to protected resources), and, finally, he logout. The transition system (of the Figure 3.1) describes the conversations allowed by the login service, but CA-Rules are needed to fully describe the process of this service. In particular, some actions (e.g. *login*, or, *activateAccount*) may need of preconditions, e.g. a user can log into the service only if he has an active account.

■

Of course, there exist more sophisticated examples, where several actions, even nondeterministic, can be executed in a state. The nondeterminism are used to model the partial knowledge about the service internal logic.

The second element characterizing the process of a DAS is the set of *Condition-Action Rules* (CA-Rules). Differently from DCDSs, where the set of CA-Rules is intended to specify in a declarative way the process implemented by the system, here this set is used only for validating the action parameters. In details, the Condition-Action Rule associated to an action $\alpha \in \mathcal{A}$ has the form $Q \mapsto \alpha$, where Q is First-Order query over \mathcal{R} . The free variables of Q are exactly the parameters of α , and whose other terms can be quantified variables or constants of $\text{ADOM}(\mathcal{I}_0)$. We assume that for each action can be defined at most one rule³.

Example 3.2.3. We complete the example 3.2.2 by presenting the rest of the system. The data layer of the service *login* is intended to store the credentials of the users and to keep track of the their account status. In details, the data layer can be described by:

- \mathcal{C} which is the set of all possible strings accepted by a C-language compiler.;
- $\mathcal{R} = \{\text{User}(\text{emailAddress}, \text{password}, \text{accountStatus})\}$ where the relation *User* maintains the credentials of the users registered in the system and the field *accountStatus* can assume the value: “ACCEPTED”, “REFUSED”, “ACTIVE” or “ONLINE”;
- $\mathcal{E} = \emptyset$ and $\mathcal{I}_0 = \{\}$.

We refer to the example 3.2.2 for the description of the potential conversations allowed by the service. In the following we detail the actions that the service exposes together with their preconditions. The action *login* (resp. *logout*) allows registered users to access to (resp. release) the protected resources. This action can be performed if the credentials passed as input parameters refer to an “ACTIVE” (resp. “ONLINE”) account and changes the user status to “ONLINE” (resp. “ACTIVE”). The action *requestRegistration* invokes the external services *INemail()* and *INpass()* allowing new users to insert the desired credentials and the external service *decide()* that invokes the human monitor intended to accept or refuse the request of registration. As effect of this action, a tuple of the relation *User* is stored in the database. The action *activateAccount* can be used to get a confirm of the account activation (for instance, it can be invoked by the e-mail confirmation typically sent by this kind of services). The execution of *activateAccount* requires that the registration of the user is already *accepted* and causes the changing of the account status. Finally, with the action *retry* the user can delete the *refused* registration request.

The action layer of *login* is specified by:

- $\mathcal{F} = \{\text{decide}(\text{email}, \text{pass}), \text{INemail}(), \text{INpass}()\}$, the interface *decide* invokes a human monitor that can accept or refuse a request for registration,

³Obviously, in presence of multiple rules, they can be reduced to one by OR-ing the queries.

the service call returns “ACCEPTED” or “REFUSED”, respectively. IN-email and INpass allows new users to insert their credentials.

- $\mathcal{A} = \{login(email,pass), logout(email,pass), retry(email,pass), requestRegistration(), activateAccount(email,pass)\}$ where the actions are defined as follows:

- $login(email,pass) : \{$
 User(email, pass, ACTIVE) \rightsquigarrow
 {not User(email,pass,ACTIVE), User(email,pass,ONLINE)}
 }
- $logout(email,pass) : \{$
 User(email, pass, ONLINE) \rightsquigarrow
 {not User(email,pass,ONLINE), User(email,pass,ACTIVE)}
 }
- $requestRegistration() : \{$
 true \rightsquigarrow {User(INemail(),INpass(),decide(email,pass))}
 }
- $retry(email, pass) : \{$
 User(email, pass, REFUSED) \rightsquigarrow
 {not User(email, pass,REFUSED)}
 }
- $activateAccount(email, pass) : \{$
 User(email, pass, ACCEPTED) \rightsquigarrow {
 not User(email, pass, ACCEPTED),
 User(email, pass,ACTIVE)}
 }

- $\varrho = \{$
 User(email,pass,ACTIVE) $\mapsto login(email,pass)$
 User(email,pass,ONLINE) $\mapsto logout(email,pass)$
 true $\mapsto requestRegistration()$
 User(email,pass,REFUSED) $\mapsto retry(email,pass)$
 User(email,pass,ACCEPTED) $\mapsto activateAccount(email,pass)$
 }

- The transition system is presented in the Figure 3.1.

■

3.3 DAS Semantics via transition systems

In order to understand the potential of the DAS formalism, we define an abstract execution semantics that determines the actual behavior of the service. Moreover, we describe the steps that the service undertakes for executing an action.

The semantics of a DAS is defined by means of a possibly infinite transition system, called *concrete transition system*, whose transitions are labeled by actions together with their input parameters, and states are labeled with database instance and a process state of the service. Such transition system represents all possible computations that the action layer can perform over the data layer.

Given a DAS $\mathcal{S} = \langle \langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{A}, \varrho, \mathbb{S}, s_0, \delta, \mathbb{F} \rangle \rangle$, the transition system $\Upsilon_{\mathcal{S}}$ expressing the semantics of \mathcal{S} is a tuple $\langle \Delta, \mathcal{R}, \Sigma, \varsigma_0, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}, db, pst, \Longrightarrow \rangle$ where:

- Δ is a countably infinite set of values;
- \mathcal{R} is a database schema;
- Σ is a set of states;
- $\varsigma_0 \in \Sigma$ is the initial state;
- \mathcal{A} is the set of actions exported by the service;
- \mathcal{B} is an infinite set of all possible parameter assignments for the actions of \mathcal{A} ;
- db is a function that, given a $\varsigma \in \Sigma$, returns the database associated to ς , which is made up of values in Δ and conform to \mathcal{R} ;
- pst is a function that, given a $\varsigma \in \Sigma$, returns the process state (belonging to \mathbb{S}) associated to ς ;
- $\Longrightarrow \subseteq \Sigma \times \mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{B} \times \Sigma$ is the transition relation between pairs of states.

In order to precisely build the concrete transition system associated to a DAS, we need of a better characterization of the behavior of the external services. First, we construct the concrete transition system under the assumption that the external services behave deterministically, i.e. the result of the external service call depends only on passed parameters, and then we assume that the external services expose a nondeterministic behavior, i.e. two calls of an external service with the same arguments may return distinct results during the same run.

3.3.1 Deterministic external services

In this Section we assume that the external services behave deterministically. This means that the evaluation of functions $f \in \mathcal{F}$, each representing an external service interface in the action layer, is independent from the moment in which the function is called. If, during the service execution, an external service is called twice with the same parameters, it must return the same value. For example, if

the external service f is invoked at a certain time by passing the value “a” and returns b , i.e. $f(a) = b$, then in all successive moments the call $f(a)$ must return b again.

State characterization. The state of the concrete transition system needs to maintain the current instance of the data layer and the current process state.

The instance of the data layer is a database made up of constants in \mathcal{C} , conforms to \mathcal{R} and satisfying the constraints in \mathcal{E} . Together with the current instance, we also need to remember all the answers we had so far return by the calls to an external services. As for the DCDSs, we recur to the set $\mathbb{S}\mathcal{C} = \{f(v_1..v_n) | f/n \in \mathcal{F} \text{ and } \{v_1..v_n\} \subseteq \mathcal{C}\}$ and the *service call map* $\mathcal{M} : \mathbb{S}\mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathcal{C}$.

A state of the *concrete* transition system is a triple $\langle \mathcal{I}, \mathcal{M}, s \rangle$, where \mathcal{I} is a valid instance for the database, \mathcal{M} is a service call map, and, s is the current process state of the system (i.e. $s \in \mathbb{S}$).

The initial state for the *concrete* transition system is $\langle \mathcal{I}, \emptyset, s_0 \rangle$.

Action execution constraints. The execution of an action of a DAS is constrained by the transition system defined by the action layer and the set of CA-Rules. The CA-Rule validates the action parameters for the action execution, whereas the transition system allows the execution of actions that form valid conversations.

Formally, let $\alpha(p_1..p_m) : \{e_1, \dots, e_n\} \in \mathcal{A}$ an action of \mathcal{S} . Assume that, the parameters of α are guarded by the rule $Q \mapsto \alpha$. Let σ be a substitution for the input parameters of α . We say that the execution of α with parameters σ is *legal* in the state $\langle \mathcal{I}, \mathcal{M}, s \rangle$ if:

1. $\langle p_1..p_m \rangle \sigma \in \text{ans}(Q, \mathcal{I})^4$, i.e. the input parameters are valid;
2. $\exists s' \in \mathbb{S}. \langle s, \alpha, s' \rangle \in \delta$, i.e. α can be executed in the state s .

Action execution effects. The action execution can be ideally split into two steps: first, an intermediate data layer instance is obtained by applying the effects without invoking the external service, and then, all instantiated calls are substituted (at once) with the effective returned values.

We denote with $\text{DO}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha, \sigma)$ the instance of the data layer obtained by executing the effects of an action α executed over \mathcal{I} with parameters σ , i.e. :

$$\begin{aligned} \text{DO}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha, \sigma) = & (\mathcal{I} - \\ & \bigcup_{q_i^+ \wedge q_i^- \rightsquigarrow \{add_i, del_i\} \in \text{EFFECTS}(\alpha) \parallel \theta \in \text{ans}((q_i^+ \wedge q_i^-)\sigma, \mathcal{I}) \parallel del_{ij} \in del_i} del_{ij} \theta \sigma) \\ & \bigcup_{q_i^+ \wedge q_i^- \rightsquigarrow \{add_i, del_i\} \in \text{EFFECTS}(\alpha) \parallel \theta \in \text{ans}((q_i^+ \wedge q_i^-)\sigma, \mathcal{I}) \parallel add_{ij} \in add_i} add_{ij} \theta \sigma \end{aligned} \quad (3.1)$$

⁴We use the notation $\langle p_1..p_m \rangle \sigma$ to denote the parameters obtained by applying the substitution σ to $\langle p_1..p_m \rangle$. Furthermore, given a FO query Q and a database instance \mathcal{I} , the answer $\text{ans}(Q, \mathcal{I})$ to Q over \mathcal{I} is the set of assignments σ from the free variables of Q to the domain of \mathcal{I} , such that $\mathcal{I} \models Q\sigma$. We treat $Q\sigma$ as a boolean query, and with some abuse of notation, we say $\text{ans}(Q, \mathcal{I}) \equiv \text{true}$ iff $\mathcal{I} \models Q\sigma$.

The instance $\text{DO}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha, \sigma)$ is obtained by deleting from \mathcal{I} the set of facts of the delete list and adding those of the add list. These facts (add_{ij} or del_{ij}) are instantiated by substituting the the action parameters through σ , and then, by applying all assignments θ that satisfy the query $q_i^+ \wedge Q_i^-$ over \mathcal{I} . Note that the instance $\text{DO}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha, \sigma)$ is formed by values from \mathcal{C} and Skolem terms, which represent external service calls.

For any of such instance, we define $\text{CALLS}(\text{DO}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha, \sigma))$ as the set of external service calls contained in $\text{DO}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha, \sigma)$. Furthermore, for a given set $\mathcal{D} \subseteq \mathcal{C}$, we denote with $\text{EVALS}_{\mathcal{D}}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha, \sigma)$ the set of substitutions replacing all service calls in $\text{DO}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha, \sigma)$ with values of \mathcal{D} , formally:

$$\text{EVALS}_{\mathcal{D}}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha, \sigma) = \{ \theta \mid \theta \text{ is a total function} \\ \theta : \text{CALLS}(\text{DO}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha, \sigma)) \rightarrow \mathcal{D} \} \quad (3.2)$$

Each substitution in $\text{EVALS}_{\mathcal{D}}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha, \sigma)$ represents a simultaneous evaluation of all service calls, where each call is replaced with an arbitrarily value selected from \mathcal{D} .

Concrete action execution. Now, we can define what happens when an action α is executed with a substitution σ for its parameters. We introduce the relation $\text{D-EXEC}_{\mathcal{S}}$ that associates concrete states of $\Upsilon_{\mathcal{S}}$ involved in the execution of an action. In details, $\langle \langle \mathcal{I}, \mathcal{M}, s \rangle, \alpha \sigma, \langle \mathcal{I}', \mathcal{M}', s' \rangle \rangle \in \text{D-EXEC}_{\mathcal{S}}$ if the following conditions hold:

1. the execution of α with the substitution σ of its parameters is legal in the state $\langle \mathcal{I}, \mathcal{M}, s \rangle$;
2. there exists an evaluation $\theta \in \text{EVALS}_{\mathcal{C}}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha, \sigma)$ compliant with \mathcal{M} , i.e. the past invocation of the service calls (recorded in \mathcal{M}) are associated through θ to the same value returned so far. Formally, θ and \mathcal{M} agree on the common values in their domains.
3. $\mathcal{I}' = \text{DO}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha, \sigma)\theta$, such that \mathcal{I}' satisfies \mathcal{R} and \mathcal{E} , i.e. the new instance of the database respects the data layer constraints.
4. there exists $\langle s, \alpha, s' \rangle \in \delta$;
5. $\mathcal{M}' = \mathcal{M} \cup \theta$, i.e the new service calls (invoked for the first time in the current transition) are recorded together with the returned value in the map.

The compatibility between \mathcal{M} and θ required in condition (2) forces the current invocation of a call to return the same result as its past invocations, thus realizing the intended deterministic semantics.

Concrete transition system construction. The *concrete transition system* $\Upsilon_{\mathcal{S}}$ expressing the semantics of $\mathcal{S} = \langle \langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{A}, \varrho, \mathbb{S}, s_0, \delta, \mathbb{F} \rangle \rangle$, it is defined by the tuple $\langle \Delta, \mathcal{R}, \Sigma, \varsigma_0, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}, \text{db}, \text{pst}, \Longrightarrow \rangle$ where:

- $\Delta = \mathcal{C}$ the domain of the transition system coincides with domain of the data layer of \mathcal{S} ;
- $\varsigma_0 = \langle \mathcal{I}_0, \emptyset, s_0 \rangle$ is the initial state for the concrete transition system;
- $\mathcal{B} \subseteq (\Delta \cup \text{und})^1 \times \dots \times (\Delta \cup \text{und})^{pmax}$ where $pmax$ is the maximum number of parameters required by an action of \mathcal{A} . We use und to represent the tuples with less than $pmax$ parameters, e.g. the tuple $\langle "a", \text{und}, \dots, \text{und} \rangle$ represents an assignment of a single parameter;
- db is such that $db(\langle \mathcal{I}, \mathcal{M}, s \rangle) = \mathcal{I}$;
- pst is such that $pst(\langle \mathcal{I}, \mathcal{M}, s \rangle) = s$;
- Σ and \implies are defined by simultaneous induction as the smallest set satisfying the following conditions:
 1. $\varsigma_0 \in \Sigma$
 2. if $\langle \mathcal{I}, \mathcal{M}, s \rangle \in \Sigma$, then for all substitution σ for the parameters of α and for all $\langle \mathcal{I}', \mathcal{M}', s' \rangle$ such that $\langle \langle \mathcal{I}, \mathcal{M}, s \rangle, \alpha \sigma, \langle \mathcal{I}', \mathcal{M}', s' \rangle \rangle \in \text{D-EXEC}_{\mathcal{S}}$, we have:
 - $\langle \mathcal{I}', \mathcal{M}', s' \rangle \in \Sigma$,
 - and $\langle \langle \mathcal{I}, \mathcal{M}, s \rangle, \alpha \sigma, \langle \mathcal{I}', \mathcal{M}', s' \rangle \rangle \in \implies$.

Intuitively, the concrete transition system of the DAS \mathcal{S} is defined by starting from the initial state $\varsigma_0 = \langle \mathcal{I}_0, \emptyset, s_0 \rangle$ and by calculating all states reached through a legal execution of an action α , i.e. $\langle \langle \mathcal{I}, \mathcal{M}, s \rangle, \alpha \sigma, \langle \mathcal{I}', \mathcal{M}', s' \rangle \rangle \in \text{D-EXEC}_{\mathcal{S}}$. Then, the same steps are repeated by considering each $\langle \mathcal{I}', \mathcal{M}', s' \rangle$, and so on. For each action α available in a process state s , the computation of the successor states is done by: getting all legal substitutions of the action parameters according to its condition-action rule; executing the instantiated action (i.e. $\text{DO}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha, \sigma)$); picking all the possible combinations of resulting values for the newly introduced service calls and filtering away those successors of the database that violate the equality constraints (i.e. $\mathcal{I}' = \text{DO}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha, \sigma)\theta$ satisfies \mathcal{R} and \mathcal{E} , where $\theta \in \text{EVALS}_{\mathcal{C}}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha, \sigma)$); and finally, generating a new state $\langle \mathcal{I}', \mathcal{M}', s' \rangle$ for each $\langle s, \alpha, s' \rangle \in \delta$.

It is worth noting that, the number of successors can be countably infinite because the service call results come from \mathcal{C} .

3.3.2 Non-deterministic external services

We now consider DASs under the assumption that external services behave *non-deterministically*. In this case, two calls of an external service with the same arguments may return distinct results during the same run. For example, if the external service $f \in \mathcal{F}$, invoked at a certain time by passing the value “a”, returns b, i.e. $f(a) = b$, then, in successive moments the call $f(a)$ may return any values from \mathcal{C} . This case captures truly nondeterministic entities, such as the human operators that accepts or refuses the registration request in the Example 3.2.2.

For the specification of the *concrete transition system* in the case of non-deterministic external services, we rely on the sets DO and EVALS defined for the deterministic case. We recall that $\text{DO}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha, \sigma)$ denotes the instance obtained by applying the effects of an action α invoked with parameters σ when the current data layer instance is represented by \mathcal{I} . Whereas, given a set $\mathcal{D} \subseteq \mathcal{C}$, the set $\text{EVALS}_{\mathcal{D}}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha, \sigma)$ denotes the set of all substitutions that replace all service calls in $\text{DO}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha, \sigma)$ with values of \mathcal{D} .

State characterization. In this case there is no need to record the past invocations of the external service calls. Therefore, a *state* $\varsigma \in \Sigma$ of the *concrete transition system* is characterized by the current instance of the database (i.e. an instance of \mathcal{R} over \mathcal{C} satisfying \mathcal{E}) and the current process state, i.e. $\varsigma = \langle \mathcal{I}, s \rangle$ where $s \in \mathbb{S}$. Consequently, the initial state of the *concrete transition system* is represented by $\varsigma = \langle \mathcal{I}_0, s_0 \rangle$.

As in the deterministic case, the execution of an action α with parameters σ is *legal* in a state $\langle \mathcal{I}, s \rangle$ if:

1. $\langle p_1..p_m \rangle \sigma \in \text{ans}(Q, \mathcal{I})$, i.e. the input parameters are valid;
2. $\exists s' \in \mathbb{S}. \langle s, \alpha, s' \rangle \in \delta$, i.e. α can be executed in the state s .

Concrete action execution. Now, we can define the semantics of an action application in the case of nondeterministic services. We introduce a transition relation $\text{N-EXEC}_{\mathcal{S}}$ between states of $\Upsilon_{\mathcal{S}}$, called *concrete execution of $\alpha\sigma$* such that $\langle \langle \mathcal{I}, s \rangle, \alpha\sigma, \langle \mathcal{I}', s' \rangle \rangle \in \text{N-EXEC}_{\mathcal{S}}$ if the following conditions holds:

1. the execution of α , with the substitution σ of its parameters, is legal in the state $\langle \mathcal{I}, s \rangle$;
2. there exists $\theta \in \text{EVALS}_{\mathcal{C}}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha, \sigma)$;
3. $\mathcal{I}' = \text{DO}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha, \sigma)\theta$ such that \mathcal{I}' satisfies \mathcal{R} and \mathcal{E} ;
4. there exists $\langle s, \alpha, s' \rangle \in \delta$.

In contrast to the deterministic services case, the evaluation θ is freely chosen. Furthermore, notice that all occurrences of the same service call, within a concrete execution step, are evaluated to the same result.

Concrete transition system construction. The *concrete transition system* $\Upsilon_{\mathcal{S}}$ expressing the semantics of $\mathcal{S} = \langle \langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{A}, \varrho, \mathbb{S}, s_0, \delta, \mathbb{F} \rangle \rangle$, in the case of nondeterministic external services, it is defined by the tuple $\langle \Delta, \mathcal{R}, \Sigma, \varsigma_0, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}, db, pst, \Longrightarrow \rangle$ where:

- $\Delta = \mathcal{C}$ the domain of the transition system coincides with domain of the data layer of \mathcal{S} ;
- $\varsigma_0 = \langle \mathcal{I}_0, s_0 \rangle$ is the initial state for the concrete transition system;

- $\mathcal{B} \subseteq (\Delta \cup \text{und})^1 \times \dots \times (\Delta \cup \text{und})^{pmax}$ where $pmax$ is the maximum number of parameters required by an action of \mathcal{A} . We use und to represent the tuples with less than $pmax$ parameters, e.g. the tuple $\langle "a", \text{und}, \dots, \text{und} \rangle$ represents an assignment of a single parameter;
- db is such that $db(\langle \mathcal{I}, s \rangle) = \mathcal{I}$;
- pst is such that $pst(\langle \mathcal{I}, s \rangle) = s$;
- Σ and \implies are defined by simultaneous induction as the smallest set satisfying the following conditions:
 1. $\varsigma_0 \in \Sigma$
 2. if $\langle \mathcal{I}, s \rangle \in \Sigma$, then for all α, σ (substitution of parameters of α) and $\langle \mathcal{I}', s' \rangle$ such that $\langle \langle \mathcal{I}, s \rangle, \alpha\sigma, \langle \mathcal{I}', s' \rangle \rangle \in \text{N-EXEC}_{\mathcal{S}}$, we have:
 - $\langle \mathcal{I}', s' \rangle \in \Sigma$,
 - and $\langle \langle \mathcal{I}, s \rangle, \alpha\sigma, \langle \mathcal{I}', s' \rangle \rangle \in \implies$.

3.4 DCDSs and DASs

In this Section we show that the evolution of the underlying data layer of a DAS can be simulated by a DCDS suitably obtained from the service description. This reduction is needed to verify the FO formulas required for checking the existence of an *Action-Delegation Relation* (cf. Section 6.2.2). More precisely, our intent is to use the well-known verification mechanism developed for DCDSs in order to check that every achievable state of the data layer of a DAS satisfies a desired FO formula.

Intuitively, a DAS can be viewed as a DCDS that can execute sequences of actions conforms with a given transition system. Therefore, at each concrete action execution step the actions allowed by a DAS are also provided by a DCDS (derived from it). Consequently, each state of the data layer state achieved by the DAS is also reached by the DCDS (i.e. the evolution of the DAS data layer is simulated by the DCDS data layer).

We start by formally defining the reduction of DAS to a DCDS that preserves the achieved data-layer instances, i.e. the obtained DCDS is able to simulate the evolution of the DAS data-layer.

Definition 1 (Data-layer preserving reduction of a DAS). Given a DAS $\mathcal{S} = \langle \langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{A}, \varrho, \mathbb{S}, s_0, \delta, \mathbb{F} \rangle \rangle$, the DCDS representing its *data-layer preserving reduction* is $\mathcal{S}_r = \langle \langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{A}, \varrho \rangle \rangle$.

It is easy to note that the DCDS is obtained by eliminating the transition system of the DAS. Now, we can provide the result that allows to verify the desired DAS FO properties over its DCDS reduction.

Theorem 1. *Given a DAS $\mathcal{S} = \langle \langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{A}, \varrho, \mathbb{S}, s_0, \delta, \mathbb{F} \rangle \rangle$ and the DCDS \mathcal{S}_r representing its data-layer preserving reduction, then the instances of the data layer achieved by \mathcal{S} are also instances of the data layer of \mathcal{S}_r .*

Proof. By induction.

- **Base Case.** By definition of data-layer preserving reduction, \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{S}_r start from the same data-layer initial instance.
- **Inductive step.** If \mathcal{I} is a data-layer instance of both \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{S}_r , then, the data-layer instances of \mathcal{S} achieved by a legal execution of an action $\alpha \in \mathcal{A}$ with parameters σ over \mathcal{I} , are also reached by \mathcal{S}_r through a legal execution $\alpha\sigma$ over \mathcal{I} .

To complete the proof we have to show that given a data-layer instance \mathcal{I} that is valid for both \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{S}_r , if $\alpha\sigma$ is a legal action execution for \mathcal{S} over \mathcal{I} , then $\alpha\sigma$ is a legal action execution for \mathcal{S}_r over \mathcal{I} . For DASs, the execution of an action α with parameters σ is *legal* in a state $\langle \mathcal{I}, s \rangle$ if:

1. $\langle p_1..p_m \rangle \sigma \in \text{ans}(Q, \mathcal{I})$, i.e. the input parameters are valid;
2. $\exists s' \in \mathbb{S}. \langle s, \alpha, s' \rangle \in \delta$, i.e. α can be executed in the state s .

Whereas, for DCDSs, the execution of an action α with parameters σ is *legal* in a state \mathcal{I} if $\langle p_1..p_m \rangle \sigma \in \text{ans}(Q, \mathcal{I})$. It is straightforward to see that the condition of legal execution for DASs implies that of DCDSs. \square

3.5 Discussion

We have proposed a formalism, called DAS, for describing service behavior in terms of the actions they can perform by paying more attention (with respect to the previous proposals) on the data involved in the service execution. Such model allows to capture the dynamic capabilities of services and specifies how its execution affects (or, is affected by) a full-fledged database. DAS offers the possibility of describing a wide range of real scenarios.

We have defined an abstract execution semantics of DASs in terms of possibly infinite transition systems. This was essential in order to determine the actual behavior of the service.

Finally, we have showed an approach for using the well-known verification mechanism developed for DCDSs in order to check that every possible state of a DAS data layer satisfies a desired FO formula. This method is based on the reduction of a DAS to a DCDS that can simulate the evolution of its data layer. This approach offers a method for verifying properties concerning with data aspects and it can be accompanied by a standard model checking techniques (e.g. μ -calculus) for providing a complete verification mechanism.

Chapter 4

Basic Multi-DAS System

In this Chapter, we introduce the fundamental blocks constituting the core of our framework that will be detailed in the following chapters. Furthermore, we present the problem of composing a finite set of data-aware services (DAS) so to devise a new composite DAS. We discuss our assumptions in tackling this problem, in particular, we face the particular case of available services that share a common data layer. We introduce the Multi-DAS System, a component that allow us to describe, in terms of DAS language, the overall behavior of a community of available DASs that share a common data layer.

4.1 Introduction to the framework

In this Section we introduce the problem of data-aware service composition and we present the fundamental blocks which constitutes the core of our framework.

Data-Aware Services. A *Data-Aware Service* (or DAS) is a software system that interacts with its clients in order to achieve a specific goal. It is made up of a program that manipulates data stored in a possibly shared database. DASs publish their behavior in order accomplish the service composition purposes. A DAS can capture the typical scenario in which the execution of a program is affected by data. For a complete description of the Data-Aware Services refer to Chapter 3.

Data-Aware Service Composition. It is the problem of automatically combining a set of available data-aware services so to realize a desired service. The latter is a *virtual* service, therefore the fragments of its execution must be suitably mimed by the available services. Furthermore, the available services must evolve their databases so to allow to reconstruct, at each step, the target database.

Multi-DAS System. A *Multi-DAS System* is a group of available data-aware services that share a common data layer. The services share both the data schema (relational schema, initial database instance) and the current database instance by accessing to the same database management system (DBMS). Although the available services are independent components, the execution of the database updates have to follow the scheduling imposed by the DBMS. For this reason, we model this system so to execute only one action at a time, in other words, we assume that the services, belonging to the same Multi-DAS system, cannot execute actions in a real concurrent environment. Technically, the actions executed by a Multi-DAS system can be viewed as atomic *Stoered Procedures* that are invoked by the services, and then, scheduled by the DBMS.

A *Multi-DAS System* can be defined by the shared data layer and the so-called *execution model* which characterizes the actions that can perform together with the allowed conversations.

Target DAS. It is a virtual service for which exists only the behavioral specification expressed in the DAS formalism. In order to execute the service every fragments of its computation must be delegated to an available (and existing) service.

Orchestrator. The Orchestrator is the software component intended to coordinate the execution of a Multi-DAS system so to realize a target DAS. It keeps track (at running time) of the state of the Multi-DAS system, and, at the request of a target action it instructs the system to perform an action among those allowed in the current state. In other words, at each step, the Orchestrator delegates the target action to an appropriate action of the Multi-DAS system available in its current state.

Action-Delegator. The Action-Delegator is the software component intended to associate each target action to (at least) a delegate action (of the Multi-DAS system). It provides delegate actions that realize target specifications in every state of the system. The delegate actions guarantee the correct execution of the service and evolve the database as described by the target actions.

Composition Engine. The Composition Engine is the software component intended to synthesize the Orchestrator and the Action-Delegator program from the behavioral description of the Multi-DAS system and the target DAS.

4.2 Data-aware service composition

In the service oriented approach, a service can be interpreted as a procedure (or method) in programming languages, therefore, a set of services as a sort of programming library. This similarity is the basis of the service composition problem: as exactly as in a programming language procedures/methods are

combined to produce more complex procedures/methods, so services can be combined to build more complex services.

Service Composition can be defined as the problem of automatically combining a set of available services, so to devise a more complex service, according to a desired specification (called target).

In this thesis we face to the problem of composition of Data-Aware Services (DAS), as those presented in the Chapter 3. These services are characterized by two layers, namely, the *data layer* that stores relevant information for the service, and, the *action layer* which is essentially a program that interacts with a client and evolves (through the execution of actions requested by the client) the data layer. An important aspect to consider when dealing the composition of this kind of services is that, the database represents the communication channel through which the client get the results of the operations computed by the service. The client, by repeatedly invoking the execution of service actions, causes the progression of the data layer with, possibly, the input of new values. Then, the clients are interested to use (in a read-only mode) the current instances for them purposes. Therefore, in order to realize the behavior of a target service, the data layers of the available services are to be combined to mimic evolution of the target data layer, so to allow to construct, at any time, the current target database from the available ones. This approach originates two main questions:

1. *How to reconcile the data layers of the available services with the target one?*
2. *How to compose the dynamic behavior and the data management capabilities of the available services in order to realize the target behavior?*

The first problem is more difficult to handle since it involves additional issues related to the data-integration research area. Since the purpose of this thesis is to propose a starting point for analyzing the problem of data-aware service composition we remand the confrontation with this issue (cf. Section 7.2.3). In fact, we assume that the available services and the target service share a common data layer. In this simplified scenario, there is only one database to evolve through the actions of the available services.

For the second problem, we propose an approach based on the idea of assimilating the available services to a unique entity, called Multi-DAS system. This can be described as a common DAS since it has a data layer, which is the shared one, and an action layer, which describes the inter-related dynamic behavior of the available services (i.e. the *execution model*). Once the Multi-DAS system is defined the composition problem can be reduced to the problem of checking if the behavior of the target DAS can be delegated to the system.

4.2.1 Data-aware service composition examples

Example 4.2.1. Consider a group of services of an university that allow student to manage their university carrier. In details, the group is formed by: the *login* service that allows students to access to the other services (cf. 3.2.3), the *SISPE*

service that allows students to book for the exams, and, the *GOMP* service that allows students to manage their study plan. The services share a common data layer $\mathcal{D} = \langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle$ that stores the student information. It can be defined as follows:

- \mathcal{C} is the set containing all alphanumeric strings;
- \mathcal{R} contains the following relations:
 1. *Student*(*StudentId*, *Pass*, *Status*) stores the information about the student account.
 2. *StatusGOMP*(*StudentId*) keeps track of the user that is currently accessed to the GOMP service;
 3. *ExamCall*(*Course*, *Date*) maintains the information about the exam calls;
 4. *StudyPlan*(*Course*, *Mark*) stores the information about the study plan of the student together with the marks of the exams that he have already passed. *Mark* can store a number between 18 and 31 or the special string “*todo*”.
 5. *ExamCallReservation*(*Exam*, *Day*, *Evaluation*) stores the exam reservations done by the student together with the evaluation of the examiner;
 6. *Course*(*Name*) stores the courses provided by the university. We identify an exam with the course name it refer to.
- $\mathcal{E} = \emptyset$ and the initial instance \mathcal{I}_0 contains a finite set of credentials of students who have the access to the services, a finite set of exam calls and a finite set of courses.

SISPE allows a student both to book for the exam calls, i.e. *bookExamCall*, and, after the examiner evaluation (modeled with the external service *evaluate*() that returns a number between 0 and 31), to *register* the result. Moreover, the student through *SISPE* can *delete* an exam call reservation. *GOMP* allows a student to manage his study plan. This service provide its own login/logout operations (i.e. *loginGOMP* and *logoutGOMP* verify that the student is registered) that are intended to store the student information needed for the service execution. Furthermore, *GOMP* provides the operations for add e delete the exams from the study plan of a student. For the description of the *login* refer to the Example 3.2.3. Formally, the action layer of *SISPE* is defined by $\mathcal{P}_s = \langle \mathcal{F}_s, \mathcal{A}_s, \varrho_s, \mathbb{S}_s, s_0^s, \delta_s, \mathbb{F}_s \rangle$ and that of *GOMP* is $\mathcal{P}_g = \langle \mathcal{F}_g, \mathcal{A}_g, \varrho_g, \mathbb{S}_g, s_0^g, \delta_g, \mathbb{F}_g \rangle$. The Table 4.1 shows the description of the actions of the services and the Figures 4.1a and 4.1b depict their transition systems. The action layer of the systems is completed by the CA-Rules. The set ϱ_s of CA-Rules for *SISPE* contains:

- $\text{Student}(s, \text{pass}, \text{“ONLINE”}) \wedge \text{StudyPlan}(e, \text{“todo”}) \wedge \text{ExamCall}(e, d) \mapsto \text{bookExamCall}(e, s, d, \text{pass});$

SISPE Action Set \mathcal{A}_s	GOMP Action Set \mathcal{A}_g
$bookExamCall(e,s,d,pass):\{$ $\quad true \rightsquigarrow$ $\quad \{ExamCallReservation(e,d,evaluate())\}$ $\}$	$loginGOMP(s,pass):\{$ $\quad true \rightsquigarrow \{StatusGOMP(s)\}$ $\}$
$register(e,s,d,pass):\{$ $\quad StudyPlan(e,mark) \rightsquigarrow$ $\quad \{not\ StudyPlan(e,mark)\}$ $\quad ExamCallReservation(e,d,mark) \rightsquigarrow$ $\quad \{StudyPlan(e,mark)\}$ $\}$	$logoutGOMP(pass):\{$ $\quad StatusGOMP(s) \rightsquigarrow \{not\ StatusGOMP(s)\}$ $\}$
$delete(e,s,d,pass):\{$ $\quad ExamCallReservation(e,d,mark) \rightsquigarrow$ $\quad \{not\ ExamCallReservation(e,d,mark)\}$ $\}$	$addCourse(c,pass):\{$ $\quad true \rightsquigarrow \{StudyPlan(c,“todo”)\}$ $\}$
	$deleteCourse(c,pass):\{$ $\quad StudyPlan(c,mark) \rightsquigarrow$ $\quad \{not\ StudyPlan(c,mark)\}$ $\}$

Table 4.1: SISPE action set and GOMP action set

- $Student(s,pass,“ONLINE”) \wedge StudyPlan(e,“todo”) \wedge ExamCallReservation(e,d,m) \wedge 18 \leq m \leq 31 \mapsto register(e,s,d,pass);$
- $Student(s,pass,“ONLINE”) \wedge \exists m.ExamCallReservation(e,d,m) \mapsto delete(e,s,d,pass).$

The set ρ_g of CA-Rules for GOMP contains:

- $(Student(s,pass,“ACTIVE”) \vee Student(s,pass,“ONLNE”)) \mapsto loginGOMP(s,pass);$
- $(Student(s,pass,“ACTIVE”) \vee Student(s,pass,“ONLNE”)) \wedge StatusGOMP(s) \mapsto logoutGOMP(pass);$
- $(Student(s,pass,“ACTIVE”) \vee Student(s,pass,“ONLNE”)) \wedge StatusGOMP(s) \wedge Course(c) \mapsto addCourse(c,pass);$
- $(Student(s,pass,“ACTIVE”) \vee Student(s,pass,“ONLNE”)) \wedge StatusGOMP(s) \mapsto deleteCourse(c,pass).$

Suppose that the University decides to unify *login*, *SISPE* and *GOMP* under an unique service called *INFOSTUD*. The desired behavior of INFOSTUD is described by $\mathcal{S}_i = \langle \langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}_i, \mathcal{A}_i, \rho_i, \mathbb{S}_i, s_0^i, \delta_i, \mathbb{F}_i \rangle \rangle$ where:

- $\mathcal{F}_i = \{evaluate(), decide(student, pass), INidl(), INpass()\}$
- $\mathcal{A}_i = \{login, logout, loginGOMP, logoutGOMP, register, delete, bookExamCall, addCourse, deleteCourse\}$
- The transition system of is showed in the Figure 4.1c;

Figure 4.1: The transition systems for SISPE(4.1a), GOMP(4.1b) and the two versions of INFOSTUD(4.1c,4.1d)

- Suppose that the CA-Rules defined by INFOSTUD are the same given for the available services except for that associated to *deleteCourse*. In fact, INFOSTUD verifies that the exam has not been passed yet.

$$(Student(s, pass, "ACTIVE") \vee Student(s, pass, "ONLINE")) \wedge StatusGOMP(s) \wedge StudyPlan(c, "todo") \mapsto deleteCourse(c, pass)$$

It can be easily noted that every conversation allowed by INFOSTUD can be delegated to the available services. In order to accomplish this delegation in the data-aware case, we need an additional condition verifying that it is always possible to perform a delegate-action when the target action can be executed. Except for the action *deleteCourse*, INFOSTUD defines the same CA-Rules as the available systems, it is straightforward to see that for these actions the previous condition holds. Whereas for *deleteCourse*, it is easy to note that the condition defined by INFOSTUD implies that of GOMP. Therefore, we can conclude that INFOSTUD can be realized by *login*, *SISPE* and *GOMP*.

■

Example 4.2.2. Suppose that the University desires to deliver a new version of INFOSTUD, called INFOSTUDv2, allowing a new login (resp. logout) action,

called loginAll (resp. logoutAll), which is capable of accessing to (resp. leaving) both the login service and to the GOMP service within a single execution step. The Table 4.2 defines loginAll and logoutAll. The conversations for

loginAll	logoutAll
$loginAll(s,pass):\{$ $ true \rightsquigarrow \{StatusGOMP(s)\}$ $ Student(s, pass, "ACTIVE") \rightsquigarrow$ $ \{not Student(s,pass,"ACTIVE"),$ $ Student(s,pass,"ONLINE")\}$ $\}$	$logoutAll(s,pass):\{$ $ StatusGOMP(s) \rightsquigarrow \{not StatusGOMP(s)\}$ $ Student(s, pass, "ONLINE") \rightsquigarrow$ $ \{not Student(s,pass,"ONLINE"),$ $ Student(s,pass,"ACTIVE")\}$ $\}$

Table 4.2: loginAll and logoutAll specification

INFOSTUDv2 are specified by the figure 4.1d. The CA-Rules associated to the new actions are defined as follows:

- $Student(s,pass,"ACTIVE") \mapsto loginAll(s,pass)$
- $StatusGOMP(s) \wedge Student(s,pass,"ONLINE") \mapsto logoutAll(pass)$

The Figure 4.2 shows a possible composition of login, SISPE and GOMP that realizes INFOSTUDv2. loginAll (resp. logoutAll) can be delegated to a composed execution in which login (resp. logout) is performed after loginGOMP (resp. logoutGOMP). Once the loginAll operation is performed each target action can be delegated to the corresponding action of the available services. The execution

Figure 4.2: A possible composition of login, SISPE and GOMP that realizes INFOSTUDv2

of the action loginAll can be delegated to the login service and the GOMP service because each effect of loginAll is performed by either login or loginGOMP. Moreover, it easy to note that when a database instance satisfies the CA-Rule associated to loginAll, it satisfies those of login and loginGOMP too.

■

As showed by the examples above, the composition of data-aware services involves two different problems. The first, called *Action-Delegation Problem*, is

Figure 4.3: An example of Multi-DAS system

concerned with finding suitable actions that update the database as a target action describes, e.g. the union of *login* and *loginGOMP* realizes the effects of *loginAll*. Furthermore, a solution of this problem guarantees that every data layer instance satisfying the target CA-Rule permits the execution of the delegate actions. In our framework this issue is faced by the so-called Action-Delegator, presented in the Chapter 6.

The second, called *Behavioral Composition*, is concerned with checking that every target conversation can be realized by suitably delegate the execution of its actions to the available services. It is essentially the problem faced by the Roman model, but in our framework the Orchestrator uses the Action-Delegator in order to associates a target action to an appropriate available one. The Orchestrator will be presented in the Chapter 6.

4.3 Multi-DAS System formalization

A *Multi-DAS System* is a (finite) community of available data-aware services that share a common data layer. The Figure 4.3 shows an example of Multi-DAS system composed by n data-aware services. The services share both the data schema (relational schema, initial database instance) and the current database instance by accessing to the same database management system (DBMS). Although the available services are independent components, the execution of the database updates have to follow the scheduling imposed by the DBMS. For this reason, we model the Multi-DAS system so to execute only one action at a time, in other words, we assume that the services, belonging to the same Multi-DAS system, cannot execute actions in a real concurrent environment. Technically, the actions executed by system can be viewed as atomic *Stored Procedures* that are invoked by the services, and then, scheduled by the DBMS.

A *Multi-DAS System* can be defined by the shared data layer and the so-called *execution model* which characterizes the actions that the system can perform together with the conversations allowed by it. Intuitively, the system

characterizes the overall behavior of the services, so, its actions, external services and CA-Rules are obtained from the union of those of the available services. Instead, the transition system is calculated through the asynchronous product of those defined by the available services.

Definition 2 (Multi-DAS system). Given a finite community C of n data-aware services $C = \{\mathcal{S}_1, \dots, \mathcal{S}_n\}$, where $\mathcal{S}_i = \langle \langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}_i, \mathcal{A}_i, \varrho_i, \mathbb{S}_i, s_0^i, \delta_i, \mathbb{F}_i \rangle \rangle$ (for $i \in [1..n]$), the **Multi-DAS system** defining the overall behavior of the services is defined as:

$$\mathcal{S}_s = \langle \langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}_s, \mathcal{A}_s, \text{EX}, \varrho_s, \mathbb{S}_s, s_0^s, \delta_s, \mathbb{F}_s \rangle \rangle$$

where:

- $\mathcal{F}_s = \bigcup_{i \in [1..n]} \mathcal{F}_i$ is the set of external service interfaces used by the actions of the external services;
- \mathcal{A}_s is the set of actions exported by the system that is built by joining the action set of the available services. Since an action α might be exported by multiple services each defining a (possibly) different CA-Rule, we choose to assign a unique identifier to each pair $\langle \text{action}, \text{service} \rangle$ in order to distinguish where the action comes from.

$$\mathcal{A}_s = \{ \alpha \mid \alpha \text{ is the unique identifier associated to the pair } \langle \alpha_i, j \rangle \text{ s.t.} \\ \alpha_i \in \mathcal{A}_j \text{ where } i \in [1..n] \}$$

We use the function id to associate the action identifiers, i.e. in the above definition $\text{id}(\alpha) = \alpha_i$.

- $\text{EX} : \mathcal{A}_s \rightarrow \{1, \dots, n\}$ is a total function that associates every action of \mathcal{A}_s to the identifier of the available service to which the action comes from;
- $\varrho_s = \bigcup_{i \in [1..n]} \varrho_i$ is the set of the CA-Rules for the action set \mathcal{A}_s ¹;
- $\mathbb{S}_s = \mathbb{S}_1 \times \dots \times \mathbb{S}_n$ is the set of system state;
- $s_0^s = \langle s_0^1 \dots s_0^n \rangle$ is the system initial state;
- $\mathbb{F}_s = \mathbb{F}_1 \times \dots \times \mathbb{F}_n$ is the system final states;
- $\delta_s \subseteq \mathbb{S}_s \times \mathcal{A}_s \times \mathbb{S}_s$ is the system transition relation, where $\langle s^1 \dots s^n \rangle \xrightarrow{\alpha} \langle s^{1'} \dots s^{n'} \rangle \in \delta_s$ iff there exists $k \in \{1..n\}$ such that:
 - $\langle s^k, \text{id}^{-1}(\alpha), s^{k'} \rangle \in \delta_k$;
 - $s^j = s^{j'}$ for each $j = 1..n$ such that $j \neq k$.

¹We assume that, the CA-Rules belonging to the sets ϱ_i are translated to support the action identification introduced by \mathcal{A}_s .

$a(p_1)$	$b(p_1)$	$c()$
$a(p_1):\{$ $B(x,p_1) \rightsquigarrow A(x)$ $\}$	$b(p_1):\{$ $A(x) \rightsquigarrow B(x,f(p_1))$ $\}$	$c():\{$ $A(x) \rightsquigarrow C(x)$ $\}$

Table 4.3: Definition of the available actions

Intuitively, given a state $\langle s^1 \dots s^n \rangle \in \mathbb{S}_s$, the system \mathcal{S}_s can execute an operation if and only if there exists one service \mathcal{S}_k (among $\mathcal{S}_1, \dots, \mathcal{S}_n$) that can do it in s^k .

In the Roman model all the services in a community share a common understanding set of operation alphabet. Instead, in the proposed framework, each service can define a set of actions that is independent from the other ones without any constraints on the action names, i.e. two actions with different names can have the same effect specification.

Example 4.3.1. Let \mathcal{C} be the group of available services formed by *srv1*, *srv2* and *srv3* defined over the same data layer. The data layer $\langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle$ is defined as follows:

- \mathcal{C} is the set of all alphanumeric strings;
- $\mathcal{R} = \{A \setminus 1, B \setminus 2, C \setminus 1\}$;
- $\mathcal{I}_0 = \emptyset$ and $\mathcal{E} = \emptyset$;

The action layer of the services are defined by:

- $\mathcal{F}_{srv1} = \mathcal{F}_{srv2} = \mathcal{F}_{srv3} = \{f \setminus 1\}$
- $\mathcal{A}_{srv1} = \{a, b\}$, $\mathcal{A}_{srv2} = \{a, b, c\}$, $\mathcal{A}_{srv3} = \{b\}$ where a, b and c are defined in the Table 4.3.
- $\varrho_{srv1} = \{A(p_1) \mapsto a(p_1), A(p_1) \mapsto b(p_1)\}$,
 $\varrho_{srv2} = \{A(p_1) \mapsto a(p_1), A(p_1) \mapsto b(p_1), true \mapsto c\}$,
 $\varrho_{srv3} = \{A(p_1) \mapsto b(p_1)\}$;
- The transition systems are showed in Figure 4.4;

The Multi-DAS system \mathcal{S}_s that unifies the capabilities of the group \mathcal{C} is defined as follows:

$$\mathcal{S}_s = \langle \langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}_s, \mathcal{A}_s, \text{EX}, \varrho_s, \mathbb{S}_s, s_0^s, \delta_s, \mathbb{F}_s \rangle \rangle$$

where:

- $\mathcal{F}_s = \{f \setminus 1\}$;
- $\mathcal{A}_s = \{a, b, c\}$;

Figure 4.4: Transition systems of the available services

Figure 4.5: The transition system for the Multi-DAS System \mathcal{S}_s .

- $\varrho_s = \{A(p_1) \mapsto a(p_1), A(p_1) \mapsto b(p_1), true \mapsto c\}$;
- The transition system for \mathcal{S}_s is showed in the Figure 4.5;

■

4.4 Discussion

In this Chapter, we have presented the fundamental blocks constituting the core of our framework. Some of these will be detailed in the following chapters.

Furthermore, we have discussed the problem of composing a finite set of data-aware services (DAS) so to devise a new composite DAS, namely, the problem of the Data-Aware Service Composition, together with the assumptions

in tackling this problem. In particular, we face the special case of available services that share a common data layer.

We have introduced the Multi-DAS System, a component that allow us to describe, in terms of the DAS language, the overall behavior of a finite group of available DASs sharing a common data layer. This approach gives the possibility of reducing the problem of checking the existence of a composition that realizes a target DAS, to the problem of verifying that the behavior of a target service can be delegated to a Multi-DAS system (essentially another DAS). This system is equipped with a basic execution model in which the system executes the actions of the available one by one, i.e. each execution step of the system corresponds to one execution step of a service. This model will be extended in the Chapter 5 where the execution steps of the system will be associated to a composite execution of the service actions.

Chapter 5

Multi-DAS System with Compounded Actions

In this Chapter we propose a technique for extending the Multi-DAS system capabilities by providing new actions that are derived from the existing ones. The Multi-DAS system presented in the Chapter 4 is characterized by an execution model in which the actions exported by the system are exactly those of the available services, and, they are intended to be executed singularly, i.e. each execution step of the system corresponds to one execution step of a service. Indeed, this kind of systems allows to define an extended execution model in which each execution step of the Multi-DAS system may correspond to the execution of many available actions.

In particular, we present two execution models, each one characterized by a different manner of executing the component actions. In the first model (called “*Concurrent Execution Model*”), the component actions are intended to be executed *concurrently*, whereas, in the second (called *Sequential Execution Model*), they are intended to be executed *sequentially*.

We provide a formal specification of actions that are suitable for combination and we devise a straightforward syntactic condition able to check if the component actions can be executed together.

This approach represents a significant improvement with respect to the existing composition techniques which treat the actions singularly.

5.1 Compounded Actions

In the Chapter 4, we have presented the basic formalization of a Multi-DAS System. This is characterized by an execution model in which the actions exported by the system are exactly those of the services, and, they are intended to be executed singularly, i.e. each execution step of the system corresponds to one execution step of a service. Indeed, this kind of systems allows to define an extended execution model in which each execution step of the Multi-DAS

system may correspond to the execution of many available actions. In doing so, each action of the system is associated to a set of actions of the available services that executes it. We identify with the name “*component actions*” those of the available services and with “*compounded action*” that of the Multi-DAS system derived by the combination of the previous ones.

In particular, we present two execution models each one characterized by a different manner of executing the component actions. In the first model (called Concurrent Execution Model), the component actions are intended to be executed *concurrently*, whereas, in the second (called Sequential Execution Model), they are intended to be executed *sequentially*.

We require that, any compounded action has to operate as an atomic one, in other words, from a point of view external to the Multi-DAS system, an observer (a client, or a service) must not be able to distinguish the executions of the compounded actions from that of an atomic one providing the same effects.

For instance, consider the Example 4.2.2, the *login* service exports *login* and the *GOMP* service exports its own login operation, called *loginGOMP*. The two actions can be combined so to derive a new operation, called *loginAll*, that accesses to both services in a single execution step. This combination is needed in order to realize the operation desired by INFOSTUDv2. For congruency issues (that will be introduced later in this Chapter), the components of *loginAll* are to be executed sequentially.

As showed in the previous example, the effect specification of a compounded action can be obtained by joining the specifications of its components. Clearly, not all actions are suited for combination, some of them might arise congruency issues, e.g. consider two concurrent actions that update the same tuple, the effect of their execution might change due to the schedule of the two actions. To be precise, we consider *legal* any compounded action that, for any schedule of its components, the overall effect of its execution results as an execution of an atomic action. This requirement can be traduced in a syntactic condition, called *Effect Compliance*, among the effect specification of the action components. Each execution model defines its own condition characterizing the legal compounded actions.

Furthermore, the parameters of a compounded action can be obtained by concatenating the parameters of its components. Therefore, the parameter assignment of a compounded action has to specify which is the value associated to each parameter of its components. A possible implementation of the Multi-DAS system may need of an intermediate software component that is intended to capture the requests for the compounded action, and, to invoke the execution the components with the appropriate parameters. In our framework, this component is included in the Orchestrator, but, since this aspect is irrelevant with respect to the composition problem, we do not detail it.

In order to find new compounded actions for a given Multi-DAS system $\mathcal{S}_s = \langle \langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}_s, \mathcal{A}_s, \text{EX}, \varrho_s, \mathbb{S}_s, s_0^s, \delta_s, \mathbb{F}_s \rangle \rangle$, we proceed as follows:

1. For each subset *acts* of atomic actions of \mathcal{A}_s (i.e. $\text{acts} \subseteq \mathcal{A}_s$), we check if *acts* meets the requirements of the legal compounded actions (either

for the concurrent or the sequential ones).

2. We define the set of states $\mathbb{S}_{\text{acts}} \subseteq \mathbb{S}_s$ from where it is possible to execute `acts`.
3. For each state of $s \in \mathbb{S}_{\text{acts}}$, we define the set of states $\mathbb{S}_{\text{acts}}^s \subseteq \mathbb{S}_s$ achieved through the execution of `acts` in s .
4. For each pair $(s, \mathbb{S}_{\text{acts}}^s)$, we add $|\mathbb{S}_{\text{acts}}^s|$ transitions to δ_s , each representing an execution of `acts` in the state s ;
5. For each `acts`, we define the CA-Rule that is to be satisfied for executing all of its components. It can be obtained by AND-ing the query associated of CA-Rule of the components of `acts`, e.g. suppose that the action `acts` is composed by $\alpha_1.. \alpha_n$, and, the CA-Rules¹ associated to the $\alpha_1.. \alpha_n$ are $Q_{\alpha_1}(\vec{p}_1) \mapsto \alpha_1(\vec{p}_1), \dots, Q_{\alpha_n}(\vec{p}_n) \mapsto \alpha_n(\vec{p}_n)$; therefore the CA-Rule to be associated to `acts` is the following:

$$Q_{\alpha_1}(\vec{p}_1) \wedge \dots \wedge Q_{\alpha_n}(\vec{p}_n) \mapsto \text{acts}(\vec{p}_1 \dots \vec{p}_n)$$

Intuitively, when the CA-Rule of `acts` is satisfied, the CA-Rules of its components are satisfied.

Steps 2, 3 and 4 are accomplished by defining a condition, called *Transition Relation Compliance*.

From this procedure, it can be noted that the elements of the Multi-DAS system characterizing the execution model are: the action set \mathcal{A}_s , the transition relation δ_s , and, the set of CA-Rules ϱ_s . For each execution model, we will define a new version of these elements, i.e. for the “concurrent” execution model we will define \mathcal{A}_s^+ , δ_s^+ and ϱ_s^+ ; whereas, for the “sequential” execution model we will define \mathcal{A}_s^- , δ_s^- and ϱ_s^- .

5.1.1 Execution effects of a compounded action

Intuitively, the effects of a compounded action are the joined effects of its components. Therefore, the result of the execution of a compounded action `acts` over a database instance \mathcal{I} is obtained by removing the tuples contained in the component delete-lists, and, then, by adding those in the component add-lists.

Definition 3. Given a compounded action `acts` constituted by n atomic actions $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n$, i.e. $\text{acts}(\vec{p}_1, \dots, \vec{p}_n) = \{\alpha_1(\vec{p}_1), \dots, \alpha_n(\vec{p}_n)\}$, the set of specifications of *conditional effects*, that are required to hold once the execution of `acts` is terminated, is the joined effect of its components, i.e. :

$$\text{acts}(\vec{p}_1, \dots, \vec{p}_n) : \left\{ \bigcup_{i \in [1..n]} \text{EFFECTS}(\alpha_i) \right\}$$

¹We assume that for each action is associated one CA-Rule.

Furthermore, each component action is executed against a database instance that is modified by the other components that are previously executed. For instance, consider the compounded action $acts$ formed by the actions α_1 , α_2 and α_3 . Suppose that at request for the execution of $acts$, over the database instance \mathcal{I} , the schedule (imposed by the DBMS, in the case of the concurrent execution model, or, requested in the case of the sequential execution model) is $\alpha_1\alpha_2\alpha_3$. So, α_1 instantiates its effects with respect to \mathcal{I} , α_2 instantiates its effects with respect to the instance resulted by the execution of α_1 , and so on. Since not all effects are not instantiated w.r.t. \mathcal{I} , the overall execution of α_1 , α_2 and α_3 does not operate as an atomic action. Therefore, in order to meet the requirements, the effects of component actions are to be instantiated with respect to the same database instance, e.g. the effects α_1 , α_2 and α_3 are to be instantiated w.r.t. \mathcal{I} .

The following definition proposes a semantics of execution of a compounded action, valid for every execution model.

Definition 4. Given a compounded action $acts$ formed by n atomic actions $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n$, i.e. $acts = \{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n\}$, the instance obtained by executing the overall effects of $acts$ over the database instance \mathcal{I} , with a parameter assignment σ , is defined by $DO(\mathcal{I}, acts, \sigma)$, where:

$$DO(\mathcal{I}, acts, \sigma) = (\mathcal{I} - \bigcup_{\alpha_k \in acts} \parallel p_i \rightsquigarrow \{add_i, del_i\} \in EFFECTS(\alpha_k) \parallel \theta \in ans(p_i, \sigma, \mathcal{I}) \parallel del_{ij} \in del_i \parallel del_{ij} \theta \sigma) \cup \bigcup_{\alpha_k \in acts} \parallel p_i \rightsquigarrow \{add_i, del_i\} \in EFFECTS(\alpha_k) \parallel \theta \in ans(p_i, \sigma, \mathcal{I}) \parallel add_{ij} \in add_i \parallel add_{ij} \theta \sigma$$

It is worth to note that, the effects are instantiated with respect to \mathcal{I} since the query associated to them are executed against \mathcal{I} , i.e. $\theta \in ans(p_i, \sigma, \mathcal{I})$; and, the updates are executed against \mathcal{I} .

The following result proves that the executions of compounded actions compliant with the semantics 4 is indistinguishable from the execution of an atomic action providing the same effects of the compounded one.

Theorem 2. Given a compounded action $acts$ formed by n atomic actions $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n$, i.e. $acts = \{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n\}$, and another atomic action α such that $\alpha(\vec{p}_1, \dots, \vec{p}_n) : \left\{ \bigcup_{i \in [1..n]} EFFECTS(\alpha_i) \right\}$, we have that the execution effects of $acts$ over the database instance \mathcal{I} , with a parameter assignment σ , is indistinguishable from the execution effects of α over the database instance \mathcal{I} , with a parameter assignment σ , i.e.

$$DO(\mathcal{I}, acts, \sigma) = DO(\mathcal{I}, \alpha, \sigma)$$

Proof. From the definition of $DO(\mathcal{I}, acts, \sigma)$ (cf. 4), it can be easily obtained $DO(\mathcal{I}, \alpha, \sigma)$ (cf. 3.1). \square

Notice the generality of the result which is independent from both the database instance and the parameter assignment. Clearly, in order to meet the

requirements, every model (i.e. Concurrent or Sequential) must guarantee that the execution of compounded actions attains to the definition 4. This can be accomplished by two ways.

The first is to use a temporary storage to keep the results of the queries involved in the action execution, and then, to instantiate the effects with respect to this storage. To be more precise, the execution of $DO(\mathcal{I}, \text{acts}, \sigma)$ consists in two steps: the results of the queries p_i (of all component actions), executed against \mathcal{I} , are saved in the temporary storage, let's call it t ; then, the actions are instantiated with respect to the results maintained by t . This approach has the main drawbacks in the need of a temporary storage of an unknown size, and, in a procedure that requires of modifying the action execution, i.e. the component actions should allow to choose the database to be read.

The second is to combine only actions providing effects conforms to the desired semantics. Suppose that there exists a schedule (imposed by the DBMS or requested by the Multi-DAS system) for the component actions. Intuitively, the problem in the combined execution, over a database instance \mathcal{I} , is that the execution of the first atomic action (in the schedule) modifies \mathcal{I} , so the following actions instantiate their effects with respect to a wrong database. Indeed, this issue occurs when the first action in the schedule updates relations that will be read by the following actions in the schedule. Hence, in order to accomplish the semantics 4, it must be guaranteed that the relations modified by an action won't be read by the others. In doing so, every action component reads from relations that have not been modified with respect to \mathcal{I} , and therefore, it instantiates their effects as though it was performed over \mathcal{I} . We call this condition “*Effect Compliance*”.

In our framework, we propose a possible solution to accomplish the second approach.

5.2 Concurrent Execution Model

The Concurrent Execution Model extends the action set of a Multi-DAS system by providing compounded actions which concurrently executes their components. Since the atomic actions access to a shared resource, i.e. the database, they cannot be executed in a real concurrent environment. We refer to a notion of concurrency in the action invocation, i.e. the component actions are invoked at once. For instance, consider the actions *BookTheFlight* and *BookTheAccommodation* that are exported by a Multi-DAS system which unifies a set of services that deal with travel planning. It is reasonable to invoke concurrently these actions in order to book in a single execution step whatever is needed for a vacation. Therefore, these actions can be combined so to devise the new action *BookTheFlightAndTheAccommodation*.

5.2.1 Effect Compliance Condition for the Concurrent Execution Model

In this section, we focus only on the execution effects of a compounded action of the Concurrent Execution Model, and, for now, we assume that the transition relation of the Multi-DAS system allows to perform any schedule of the components. Our intent is to find a set of compounded actions which can be candidate to extend the action set \mathcal{A}_s . In the following section, this set will be refined by imposing the constraints required by the transition relation of the system, i.e. the so-called *Transition Relation Compliance*.

In the Concurrent Execution Model, we consider *legal* any compounded action that, for any schedule of its components, the overall effect of its execution results as an execution of an atomic action.

Some issues in concurrent execution

In the following we present some examples highlighting the issues raised by the concurrent execution of a set of actions.

Example 5.2.1. The most evident example is when the tuple added by an action is deleted by another one.

$\alpha_1():\{\$ $\text{true} \rightsquigarrow \{A(\text{INSomething}())\}$ $\}$	$\alpha_2():\{\$ $A(x) \rightsquigarrow \{\text{not } A(x)\}$ $\}$
--	--

Suppose that α_1 and α_2 are the components of the action acts , i.e. $\text{acts} = \{\alpha_1, \alpha_2\}$. Depending on the schedule of the components, the concurrent execution of α_1 and α_2 , over a database instance $\mathcal{I} = \{\}$ may lead to two different results:

1. If the schedule is $\alpha_1\alpha_2$, the instance obtained from the overall execution of acts is represented by $\mathcal{I}' = \{\}$.
2. If the schedule is $\alpha_2\alpha_1$, the instance obtained from the overall execution of acts is represented by $\mathcal{I}' = \{A(\text{INSomething}())\}$.

Only the second schedule respects the desired semantics 4. ■

Example 5.2.2. The execution of an action may cause the instantiation of additional effects of another action.

$\alpha_1():\{\$ $\text{true} \rightsquigarrow \{A(\text{INSomething}())\}$ $\}$	$\alpha_2():\{\$ $A(x) \rightsquigarrow \{B(x)\}$ $\}$
--	--

Suppose that α_1 and α_2 are the components of the action acts , i.e. $\text{acts} = \{\alpha_1, \alpha_2\}$. Depending on the schedule of the components, the concurrent execution of α_1 and α_2 , over a database instance $\mathcal{I} = \{A(a)\}$ may lead to two different results:

1. If the schedule is $\alpha_1\alpha_2$, the instance obtained from the overall execution of acts is represented by $\mathcal{I}' = \{A(a), A(\text{INSomething}()), B(a), B(\text{INSomething}())\}$.
2. If the schedule is $\alpha_2\alpha_1$, the instance obtained from the overall execution of acts is represented by $\mathcal{I}' = \{A(a), A(\text{INSomething}()), B(a)\}$.

Only the second schedule respects the desired semantics 4. ■

Example 5.2.3. The execution of an action may invalidate a CA-Rule.

$\text{Transaction}(\text{id}, \text{"Accepted"}) \mapsto$ $\text{ConfirmTransaction}(\text{id});$ $\text{ConfirmTransaction}(\text{id}): \{$ $\text{true} \rightsquigarrow \{$ $\text{not } \text{Transaction}(\text{id}, \text{"Accepted"}),$ $\text{Transaction}(\text{id}, \text{"Confirmed"}),$ $\text{Paid}(\text{id}, \text{"Accepted"})\}$ $\}$	$\exists x. \text{Transaction}(\text{id}, x) \mapsto$ $\text{Archive}(\text{id});$ $\text{Archive}(\text{id}): \{$ $\text{Transaction}(\text{id}, x) \rightsquigarrow \{$ $\text{not } \text{Transaction}(\text{id}, x),$ $\text{History}(\text{id}, x)\}$ $\}$
--	---

Table 5.1: Definitions of *ConfirmTransaction* and *Archive*.

Suppose that *ConfirmTransaction* and *Archive*, defined in the Table 5.1, are the components of the action acts , i.e. $\text{acts}(\text{id}, \text{id}) = \{\text{ConfirmTransaction}(\text{id}), \text{Archive}(\text{id})\}$. Depending on the schedule of the components, the concurrent execution of *ConfirmTransaction* and *Archive*, over a database instance $\mathcal{I} = \{\text{Transaction}(1, \text{"Accepted"})\}$ may lead to two different results:

1. If the schedule is $\text{ConfirmTransaction}(1)\text{Archive}(1)$, the instance obtained from the overall execution of acts is represented by $\mathcal{I}' = \{\text{Paid}(1), \text{History}(1)\}$.
2. If the schedule is $\text{Archive}(1)\text{ConfirmTransaction}(1)$, *ConfirmTransaction*(1) cannot be executed and the instance obtained from the overall execution of acts is represented by $\mathcal{I}' = \{\text{History}(1)\}$. ■

Intuitively, the desired execution semantics is achieved when, each action component reads from relations that have not been modified by actions previously executed. In this way, every component reads from relations that have not been modified with respect to \mathcal{I} , and therefore, it instantiates their effects as though it was performed over \mathcal{I} .

Notation

In order to formalize the problem we need to introduce some notation.

Definition 5. Let π be the schedule $\alpha_1 \dots \alpha_n$, such that $\alpha_1 \dots \alpha_n$ are executed with the same parameter assignment σ . We represent with $\text{DO}_\sigma^\mathcal{I}(\pi)$ the result of the execution of the entire schedule executed against the initial database instance \mathcal{I} , i.e.:

$$\text{DO}_\sigma^\mathcal{I}(\pi) = \text{DO}(\dots \text{DO}(\dots \text{DO}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha_1, \sigma) \dots, \alpha_i, \sigma) \dots, \alpha_n, \sigma)$$

Intuitively, α_1 performs their effects against \mathcal{I} , α_2 against the result of the execution of α_1 , and so on. Therefore, $\text{DO}_\sigma^\mathcal{I}(\pi)$ represents the overall result.

Definition 6. Let \mathcal{I} be a database instance, α an action that can update \mathcal{I} and σ a parameter assignment for α , we denote with:

- $\text{add}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha, \sigma)$ the set of the facts added by the execution of α over \mathcal{I} with a parameter assignment σ , i.e.:

$$\text{add}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha, \sigma) = \bigcup_{q_i^+ \wedge Q_i^- \rightsquigarrow \{add_i, del_i\} \in \text{EFFECTS}(\alpha)} \bigcup_{\theta \in \text{ans}((q_i^+ \wedge Q_i^-)\sigma, \mathcal{I})} \bigcup_{add_{ij} \in add_i} add_{ij}\theta\sigma$$

- $\text{del}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha, \sigma)$ the set of the facts removed by the execution of α over \mathcal{I} with a parameter assignment σ , i.e.:

$$\text{del}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha, \sigma) = \bigcup_{q_i^+ \wedge Q_i^- \rightsquigarrow \{add_i, del_i\} \in \text{EFFECTS}(\alpha)} \bigcup_{\theta \in \text{ans}((q_i^+ \wedge Q_i^-)\sigma, \mathcal{I})} \bigcup_{del_{ij} \in del_i} del_{ij}\theta\sigma$$

Definition 7. Let R be a set of names of relations and \mathcal{I} a database instance, we denote with $\text{PROJ}_R(\mathcal{I})$ the projection of \mathcal{I} with respect to the relations belonging to R .

Finally, we need to define the relations read or modified by a the execution of an action.

Definition 8. Given an action α , we denote with:

- mod_α the set of (names of) relations updated by the execution of α , i.e. those contained either in the delete lists or in the add lists.
- dep_α the set of (names of) relations from which depends the instantiation of the effects or the evaluation of the CA-Rule associated to α , i.e. the relations involved in the preconditions of the effects, those of the CA-Rule, and the relations contained in the delete lists.

Now, we can provide the formal definition of *legal* compounded action. We say that a compounded action $\text{acts} = \{\alpha_1.. \alpha_n\}$ is *legal* if, given any database instance \mathcal{I} , and any parameter assignment σ , for each schedule of its components the execution of acts over \mathcal{I} results as an execution of an atomic action. This is accomplished when the effects of each component action (in the sequence) are instantiated as though it was performed over \mathcal{I} .

Definition 9. Given a compounded action $\text{acts} = \{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n\}$, we say that acts is *legal* if for each database instance \mathcal{I} , each parameter assignment σ it results:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall \alpha_i \in \text{acts}. \forall \tau \in T(\alpha_1.. \alpha_{i-1}, \alpha_{i+1}.. \alpha_n). \\ \text{add}(\text{DO}_\sigma^\mathcal{I}(\tau), \alpha_i, \sigma) = \text{add}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha_i, \sigma) \wedge \\ \text{del}(\text{DO}_\sigma^\mathcal{I}(\tau), \alpha_i, \sigma) = \text{del}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha_i, \sigma) \end{aligned}$$

where $T(\alpha_1.. \alpha_{i-1}, \alpha_{i+1}.. \alpha_n)$ is the set containing the prefixes formed with the actions $\alpha_1.. \alpha_{i-1}, \alpha_{i+1}.. \alpha_n$.

Solutions

In order to accomplish the definition of legal compounded action is to be guaranteed that the relations modified by an action won't be read by the others. In this section we provide the results showing the correctness of this intuition.

Lemma 3. Let \mathcal{I} and \mathcal{I}' be two instances of the the same data layer, and, given an atomic action α operating over it, if $\text{PROJ}_{\text{dep}_\alpha}(\mathcal{I}) = \text{PROJ}_{\text{dep}_\alpha}(\mathcal{I}')$, then:

1. Every parameter assignment σ for α valid on \mathcal{I} is valid on \mathcal{I}' ;
2. For every valid parameter assignment σ , the execution of α over \mathcal{I} causes the same updates of the execution of α over \mathcal{I}' , i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{PROJ}_{\text{dep}_\alpha}(\mathcal{I}) = \text{PROJ}_{\text{dep}_\alpha}(\mathcal{I}') \implies \\ \text{add}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha, \sigma) = \text{add}(\mathcal{I}', \alpha, \sigma) \wedge \text{del}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha, \sigma) = \text{del}(\mathcal{I}', \alpha, \sigma) \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let $Q \mapsto \alpha$ the condition-action rule associated to α . Since the relations used by Q are contained in dep_α , and the instances of these relation in \mathcal{I} is the same of \mathcal{I}' , we have:

$$\text{ans}(Q, \mathcal{I}) = \text{ans}(Q, \mathcal{I}')$$

For 2., by exploiting the fact that the instances read for instantiating the effects are only those in $\text{PROJ}_{\text{dep}_\alpha}(\mathcal{I})$, we can show how to get $\text{add}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha, \sigma)$ from

$\text{add}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha, \sigma)$:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{add}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha, \sigma) &= \bigcup_{q_i^+ \wedge Q_i^- \rightsquigarrow \{add_i, del_i\} \in \text{EFFECTS}(\alpha)} \\
&\quad \bigcup_{\theta \in \text{ans}((q_i^+ \wedge Q_i^-)\sigma, \mathcal{I})} \bigcup_{add_{ij} \in add_i} add_{ij}\theta\sigma \\
&= \bigcup_{q_i^+ \wedge Q_i^- \rightsquigarrow \{add_i, del_i\} \in \text{EFFECTS}(\alpha)} \\
&\quad \bigcup_{\theta \in \text{ans}((q_i^+ \wedge Q_i^-)\sigma, \text{PROJ}_{\text{dep}_\alpha}(\mathcal{I}))} \bigcup_{add_{ij} \in add_i} add_{ij}\theta\sigma \\
&= \bigcup_{q_i^+ \wedge Q_i^- \rightsquigarrow \{add_i, del_i\} \in \text{EFFECTS}(\alpha)} \\
&\quad \bigcup_{\theta \in \text{ans}((q_i^+ \wedge Q_i^-)\sigma, \text{PROJ}_{\text{dep}_\alpha}(\mathcal{I}'))} \bigcup_{add_{ij} \in add_i} add_{ij}\theta\sigma \\
&= \text{add}(\mathcal{I}', \alpha, \sigma)
\end{aligned}$$

The same procedure can be applied to $\text{del}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha, \sigma)$ and $\text{del}(\mathcal{I}', \alpha, \sigma)$. \square

Theorem 4. *Let $\text{acts} = \{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n\}$ be a compounded action, acts is legal, if for every component action $\alpha_i \in \text{acts}$, the relations in dep_{α_i} are disjoint from that in $\text{mod}_{\text{acts} \setminus \{\alpha_i\}}$, i.e.*

$$\forall \alpha_i \in \text{acts}. \forall R_i \in \text{dep}_{\alpha_i}. \forall R_j \in \text{mod}_{\text{acts} \setminus \{\alpha_i\}}. R_i \sqsubseteq \neg R_j \implies \text{acts is legal}$$

Proof. By hypothesis, the relations read by α_i cannot be modified another action component, therefore, for each \mathcal{I} , for each valid parameter assignment σ and for each action schedule $\pi_{\alpha_n}^{\alpha_1}$, at the execution of i -th component action $\pi_{\alpha_n}^{\alpha_1}(i)$, we have that:

$$\text{PROJ}_{\text{dep}_{\pi_{\alpha_n}^{\alpha_1}(i)}}(\text{DO}_{\sigma}^{\mathcal{I}}(\pi_{\alpha_n}^{\alpha_1}(1).. \pi_{\alpha_n}^{\alpha_1}(i-1))) = \text{PROJ}_{\text{dep}_{\pi_{\alpha_n}^{\alpha_1}(i)}}(\mathcal{I})$$

i.e. the instance of the relations read during the execution of $\pi_{\alpha_n}^{\alpha_1}(i)$ are not updated by the execution of $\pi_{\alpha_n}^{\alpha_1}(1).. \pi_{\alpha_n}^{\alpha_1}(i-1)$. By applying the Lemma 3, we can conclude that, the updates performed by an action α at the i -th position are the same that would be executed by α at the first position. \square

5.2.2 Transition Relation Compliance for the Concurrent Execution Model

Intuitively, a state $s \in \mathbb{S}_s$ of the Multi-DAS system allows the execution of a compounded action $\text{acts} = \{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n\}$, when from s , it is possible to execute every schedule of the component actions. The Figure 5.1 shows a graphical representation of the state s . In the state s can be executed any action of acts , and, the execution of one of these leads to a state where it is still possible to perform any action of acts . This is to be accomplished for n -steps.

The definition of the states allowing the execution of a compounded action $\text{acts} = \{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n\}$ can be divided into two steps:

Figure 5.1: A graphical representation of a state s that allows the execution of a the compounded action $\text{acts} = \{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n\}$. The dashed arrows represent the transition that can be added to the relation of the Multi-DAS system.

1. Construct the set $\mathbb{S}_{\alpha_1 \dots \alpha_n} \subseteq \mathbb{S}_s$ containing the states that allow the execution of any component action $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n$;
2. Construct the set $\mathbb{S}_{\text{acts}} \subseteq \mathbb{S}_{\alpha_1 \dots \alpha_n}$, such that in each state of \mathbb{S}_{acts} can be rooted a path, constituted by n transitions, that pass only through states of $\mathbb{S}_{\alpha_1 \dots \alpha_n}$.

For each state of $s \in \mathbb{S}_{\text{acts}}$ it can be defined a set $\mathbb{S}_{\text{acts}}^s \subseteq \mathbb{S}_s$ of states of the Multi-DAS system achieved by executing acts in the state s . For each pair $(s, \mathbb{S}_{\text{acts}}^s)$, $|\mathbb{S}_{\text{acts}}^s|$ transitions (the dashed arrows in the Figure 5.1) are added to the relation δ_s^+ , i.e.:

$$\forall s' \in \mathbb{S}_{\text{acts}}^s \text{ add to } \delta_s^+ \langle s, \text{acts}, s' \rangle$$

5.3 Sequential Execution Model

The Sequential Execution Model extends the action set of a Multi-DAS system by providing compounded actions which sequentially executes its components.

For instance, consider the actions *Book* and *Pay* that are exported by a Multi-DAS system which unifies a set of services that deal with travel planning.

Book confirms the reservation for an accommodation and *Pay* transfers to the bank account of the hotel the amount needed. It is reasonable to invoke together these actions in order to confirm and pay in a single execution step the reservation. These actions can be combined so to devise the compounded action *BookAndPay*. In this case the two actions are to be executed in sequence, i.e. first the reservation is confirmed then it is paid. Therefore, we need to associate a schedule to this kind of compounded actions.

The compounded action *acts*, that causes the execution of the sequence $\alpha_1.. \alpha_n$, is denoted with $acts = [\alpha_1.. \alpha_n]$.

5.3.1 Effect Compliance Condition for the Sequential Execution Model

In this section, we focus only on the execution effects of a compounded action of the Sequential Execution Model, and, for now, we assume that the transition relation of the Multi-DAS system allows to perform any schedule of the components. Our intent is to find a set of compounded actions which can be candidate to extend the action set \mathcal{A}_s . In the following section, this set will be refined by imposing the constraints required by the transition relation of the system, i.e. the so-called *Transition Relation Compliance*.

In the Sequential Execution Model, we consider *legal* any compounded action that satisfies the following condition: *there exists a schedule of its components such that the overall effect of their execution results as an execution of an atomic action*.

Differently from the Concurrent Execution Model, in the Sequential Execution Model, the schedule of the components is required by the Multi-DAS system, and not imposed by the DBMS. Since they work with a unique schedule imposed at *compile-time*, the requirements for this kind of compounded actions are less tighter than the previous case.

Definition 10. Given a compounded action $acts = [\alpha_1, .., \alpha_n]$, we say that *acts* is *legal* if, for each database instance \mathcal{I} , each parameter assignment σ , we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall \alpha_i \in acts. \text{add}(\text{DO}_\sigma^{\mathcal{I}}(\alpha_1.. \alpha_{i-1}), \alpha_i, \sigma) &= \text{add}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha_i, \sigma) \wedge \\ &\text{del}(\text{DO}_\sigma^{\mathcal{I}}(\alpha_1.. \alpha_{i-1}), \alpha_i, \sigma) = \text{del}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha_i, \sigma) \end{aligned}$$

i.e. the execution of α_i against the database instance $\text{DO}_\sigma^{\mathcal{I}}(\alpha_1.. \alpha_{i-1})$ causes the same updates as though α_i was performed over \mathcal{I} .

In order to accomplish the definition of legal compounded action is to be guaranteed that the relations modified by an action won't be read by the actions executed later in the sequence.

Theorem 5. *Let $acts = [\alpha_1, .., \alpha_n]$ be a compounded action, $acts$ is legal, if for every component action $\alpha_i \in acts$, the relations in dep_{α_i} are disjoint from that in $\text{mod}_{\alpha_1.. \alpha_{i-1}}$, i.e.*

$$\forall \alpha_i \in acts. \forall R_i \in \text{dep}_{\alpha_i}. \forall R_j \in \text{mod}_{\alpha_1.. \alpha_{i-1}}. R_i \sqsubseteq \neg R_j \implies acts \text{ is legal}$$

Figure 5.2: A graphical representation of a state s that allows the execution of a the compounded action $\text{acts} = [\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n]$. The dashed arrows represent the transition that can be added to the relation of the Multi-DAS system.

Proof. By hypothesis, the relations read by α_i cannot be modified by an action α_j with $1 \leq j \leq i-1$. Therefore, for each \mathcal{I} , for each valid parameter assignment σ , at the execution of α_i we have that:

$$\text{PROJ}_{\text{dep}_{\alpha_i}}(\text{DO}_{\sigma}^{\mathcal{I}}(\alpha_1.. \alpha_{i-1})) = \text{PROJ}_{\text{dep}_{\alpha_i}}(\mathcal{I})$$

i.e. the instance of the relations read during the execution of α_i are not updated by the execution of $\alpha_1.. \alpha_{i-1}$. By applying the Lemma 3, we can conclude that, the updates performed by an action α_i against $\text{DO}_{\sigma}^{\mathcal{I}}(\alpha_1.. \alpha_{i-1})$ are the same that would be executed by α_i over \mathcal{I} . \square

5.3.2 Transition Relation Compliance for the Sequential Execution Model

Intuitively, a state $s \in \mathbb{S}_s$ of the Multi-DAS system allows the execution of a compounded action $\text{acts} = [\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n]$, when from s it is possible to execute α_1 , and, for every state s_1 achieved by performing α_1 in s , it is possible to execute α_2 , and so on until the entire sequence is performed. The Figure 5.2 shows a graphical representation of the state s . Formally, the state s can be defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \exists s, s_1 \in \mathbb{S}_s. \langle s, \alpha_1, s_1 \rangle \in \delta_s \wedge \\ \forall s_1. \text{ s.t. } \langle s, \alpha_1, s_1 \rangle \in \delta_s. \exists \langle s_1, \alpha_2, s_2 \rangle \in \delta_s \wedge \\ \forall s_2. \text{ s.t. } \langle s_1, \alpha_2, s_2 \rangle \in \delta_s. \exists \langle s_2, \alpha_3, s_3 \rangle \in \delta_s \wedge \\ \vdots \\ \wedge \forall s_{n-1}. \text{ s.t. } \langle s_{n-2}, \alpha_{n-1}, s_{n-1} \rangle \in \delta_s. \exists \langle s_{n-1}, \alpha_n, s' \rangle \in \delta_s \end{aligned} \quad (5.1)$$

As for the Concurrent Execution Model, for each state s satisfying the condition 5.1 can be defined the set of states $\mathbb{S}_{\text{acts}}^s$ achieved by executing acts from s . Then, for each pair $(s, \mathbb{S}_{\text{acts}}^s)$, $|\mathbb{S}_{\text{acts}}^s|$ transitions (the dashed arrows in the Figure 5.2) are added to the relation δ_s^- :

$$\forall s' \in \mathbb{S}_{\text{acts}}^s \text{ add to } \delta_s^- \langle s, \text{acts}, s' \rangle$$

$a(p_1)$	$b(p_1)$	$c()$
$a(p_1):\{$ $B(x,p_1) \rightsquigarrow A(x)$ $\}$	$b(p_1):\{$ $A(x) \rightsquigarrow B(x,f(p_1))$ $\}$	$c():\{$ $A(x) \rightsquigarrow C(x)$ $\}$

Table 5.2: Definition of the available actions

Example 5.3.1. Let \mathcal{S}_s be the Multi-DAS system presented in the Example 4.3.1. We assume that the relations A, B and C of \mathcal{R} are disjoint. The actions exported by the system are described in the Table 5.2, and, the transition system is showed in the Figure 5.3. Finally, the set of CA-Rules is $\varrho_s = \{A(p_1) \mapsto a(p_1), A(p_1) \mapsto b(p_1), true \mapsto c\}$.

Figure 5.3: The transition system for the Multi-DAS System \mathcal{S}_s .

For instance, the action set of \mathcal{S}_s can be extended with the compounded action $acts = \{b,c\}$. This two actions respects the condition of Effect Compliance defined for the Concurrent Execution Model, since:

- $dep_b = \{A\}, mod_b = \{B\}$;
- $dep_c = \{A,C\}, mod_c = \{C\}$;

Furthermore, the compounded action $acts$ can be executed from the states s_1q_1v and s_2q_1v . In the former case, the execution of $acts$ leads to the states

s_1q_2v and s_1q_1v . Whereas, in the latter case, the execution of `acts` leads to the states s_2q_2v , s_1q_2v and s_2q_1v .

■

Example 5.3.2. Let \mathcal{S} be the Multi-DAS system presented in the Example 4.3.1. An example of compounded action of the Execution Model - is `acts` = [c,a]. a and c respects the condition of Effect Compliance defined for the Sequential Execution Model, since:

- $\text{dep}_a = \{A,B\}, \text{mod}_a = \{A\};$
- $\text{dep}_c = \{A,C\}, \text{mod}_c = \{C\};$

The compounded action `acts` can be executed from the states s_1q_1v and leads to s_2q_2v .

■

5.4 Discussion

In this Chapter we have proposed a technique for extending the Multi-DAS system capabilities by providing new actions that are derived from the exiting ones. In particular, we have presented the Concurrent Execution Model which extends \mathcal{A}_s with compounded actions that concurrently executes its atomic components. Indeed, in order to guarantee that a compounded action operates as an atomic one, it is sufficient to verify that the relations modified by an action won't be read by the others. We have defined the states of the Multi-DAS system allowing the execution of a compounded action, as those from which it is possible to execute any schedule of its components.

Furthermore, we have presented the Execution Model - which extends \mathcal{A}_s by providing compounded actions that sequentially executes its atomic components. We have proved that, an action of the Sequential Execution Model operates as an atomic one, if the the relations modified by an action won't be read by the actions executed later in the sequence. Finally, we have defined the set of states allowing the execution of this kind of actions as those from which it is possible to execute the entire sequence.

Extending the action set of a Multi-DAS system with by providing compounded actions, does not add complexity to the composition task, since it can be done in a preliminary step. This task requires exponential time in the size of the action set of the Multi-DAS system.

This approach represents a significant improvement with respect to the existing composition techniques which treat the actions singularly.

Chapter 6

Action Delegation and Orchestration

In this Chapter, we provide the solution techniques for computing a data-aware service composition in the case of a common data-layer shared by the available services and the target service. We assume that the available services are unified by a Multi-DAS system that exports their overall behavior. In the Chapter 5, we have showed how to extend the Multi-DAS-system capabilities with compounded actions derived from the existing ones. We recall that, these models allow to treat the compounded actions as the atomic ones, namely, from a point of view external to the Multi-DAS system, the execution of a compounded action is indistinguishable from the execution of an atomic one that provides the same effect specification. Therefore, this result allow us to assume that the Multi-DAS system exports only atomic actions. Furthermore, we propose an approach for computing the composition synthesis that separates static (or data) aspects concerning the composition from the dynamic ones. The main focus of the static aspects is on evolving the data layer as the target DAS describes. Instead, the dynamic aspects focus only on executing conversations described by the transition system of target service. The Roman Model represents a valid method to face the latter issues. For these reasons, first, we focus only on the static aspects by considering a scenario where services allow any possible conversation (*stateless setting*); and then, by tacking advantage of the techniques developed for the stateless case and those proposed in the Roman approach, we address the case of constrained conversations (*stateful setting*).

6.1 Problem presentation

The Figure 6.1a shows a composition synthesis scenario. The Multi-DAS system is formed by N available services that access to the same data layer. Even the target service is defined with respect to the same data layer. We remark that the target service is, just, a desired behavioral specification without a corresponding

Figure 6.1: The two phases of the data-aware service composition.

software artifact able to enact it. Instead, the available services are existing software components that export their behavior by means of the DAS formalism. For clarity, in the composition phase, we assume that the available services are unified by a Multi-DAS system that exports their overall behavior. This can be accomplished as a preliminary step by the composition engine. The composition engine takes as input the description of the Multi-DAS system and the specification of the target service (also described as a DAS), and computes the composition synthesis that specifies how to delegate the target service behavior to the system.

The Figure 6.1b shows the scenario in the orchestration phase. The user of the target service (or “Target Service Client”, as called in the picture) requests for the execution of an action provided by the service and available in its current state. The request is captured by the Orchestrator, that delegates the execution of the requested action to an available service (which is invoked through the Multi-DAS system¹). The available service performs a procedure that realizes

¹We recall that, every action of the Multi-DAS system is uniquely associated to an action

the specification of the desired (target) action by, possibly, updating the current database instance and by evolving its process state. The Orchestrator decides the service to delegate the requested action on the basis of the composition synthesis and the current state of the Multi-DAS system.

From this rough formulation of the problem, we noticed some important differences with respect to the “Roman Model”. The Roman approach imposes a tight form of delegation, that is, every action of the target service must be delegated to exactly one action. The action of the target service (or *target action*) and the *delegate* action must have the same name. Precisely, the available services and the target service share a common action set. Differently, in our framework this matching is done on the basis of the specification of two actions. In this way, our approach allows to delegate the execution of the target action to more available actions. The delegate actions cooperate to realize the desired specification. This combination mechanism is embodied by the execution models introduced in the Chapter 5, that extend the action set of the Multi-DAS System with compounded actions derived from the existing ones. We recall that these models allow to treat the compounded actions as the atomic ones, namely, from a point of view external to the Multi-DAS system, the execution of a compounded action is indistinguishable from the execution of an atomic one that provides the same effect specification. Therefore, the delegation of a target action to a set of delegates can be treated as the delegation of a target action to an atomic one.

We propose an approach for computing the composition synthesis that separates static (or data) aspects concerning the composition from the dynamic ones. The main focus of the static aspects is on evolving the data layer as the target DAS describes. Instead, the dynamic aspects focus only on executing conversations described by the transition system of target service. The Roman Model represents a valid method to face the latter issues. For these reasons, first, we focus only on the static aspects by considering a scenario where services allow any possible conversation (*stateless setting*); and then, by tacking advantage of the techniques developed for the stateless case and those proposed in the Roman approach, we address the case of constrained conversations (*stateful setting*).

6.2 Stateless Setting

We call stateless every service that, at any time, can execute any action (the execution of actions does not affect the process state of the service). The process for this class of services can be specified through a single-state transition system, or, by completely ignoring it. Formally, a *stateless* DAS \mathcal{S} is defined by:

$$\mathcal{S} = \langle \langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{A}, \varrho \rangle \rangle$$

It can be noted that, a stateless DAS is essentially a DCDS.

Since the execution of an action is guarded only by CA-Rules, only the data-layer instance is relevant for defining the state of the services. Consequently,

of a available service. Therefore, from the action of the Multi-DAS system the Orchestrator can directly invoke the corresponding action of the available service.

at any time, the Multi-DAS system and the target service are in the same state because they share the same data-layer instance.

6.2.1 Service Composition in stateless setting

In the stateless setting, a composition exists when: in every data-layer state, if the target service can execute an action α_t (with some arguments), then, the Multi-DAS system must be able to perform an action α_s that realizes the effect specification of α_t . In order to realize the specification of α_t , α_s must be invoked with the same arguments passed to α_t . The purpose of the composition synthesis, in the stateless setting, is to specify which actions of the Multi-DAS system are to be executed so to evolve the data layer as the target service desires.

To formally define the service composition we recur to the semantics defined in the Chapter 3. This semantics was defined for a complete DAS, but, it can be easily reduced to the case of a stateless DAS.

Definition 11 (Trace). Given a stateless service $\mathcal{S} = \langle\langle\mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0\rangle, \langle\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{A}, \varrho\rangle\rangle$, a trace for \mathcal{S} is a possible infinite sequence of alternating database instances and instantiated actions. A trace has the following form:

$$\mathcal{I}_0 \xrightarrow{\alpha_0\sigma^0}_{\mathcal{S}} \mathcal{I}_1 \xrightarrow{\alpha_1\sigma^1}_{\mathcal{S}} \mathcal{I}_2 \cdots$$

such that, for all j :

1. $\sigma^j \in \text{ans}(Q_{\alpha_j}, \mathcal{I}_j)$, i.e. α_j can be executed against \mathcal{I}_j with parameters σ^j ;
2. $\text{DO}(\mathcal{I}_j, \alpha_j, \sigma^j)\theta = \mathcal{I}_{j+1}$, where θ is an evaluation for the external service calls in $\text{DO}(\mathcal{I}_j, \alpha_j, \sigma^j)$, i.e. the execution of α_j against \mathcal{I}_j with a valid parameter assignment σ^j , together with a valid evaluation of the external service calls in $\text{DO}(\mathcal{I}_j, \alpha_j, \sigma^j)$, evolves the database to \mathcal{I}_{j+1} ;

Intuitively, a trace represents a possible evolution of a data-aware service in the stateless setting.

Definition 12 (History). An history h is a finite prefix of a trace.

Given an history h , $\text{last}(h)$ denotes its last database instance, and $\text{length}(h)$ denotes the number of transitions it contains.

Definition 13 (Orchestrator). Let $\mathcal{S}_s = \langle\langle\mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0\rangle, \langle\mathcal{F}_s, \mathcal{A}_s, \text{EX}, \varrho_s\rangle\rangle$ be the Multi-DAS system (constituted by the stateless services $\mathcal{S}_i = \langle\langle\mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0\rangle, \langle\mathcal{F}_i, \mathcal{A}_i, \varrho_i\rangle\rangle$ for $i \in [1..n]$), let $\mathcal{S}_t = \langle\langle\mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0\rangle, \langle\mathcal{F}_t, \mathcal{A}_t, \varrho_t\rangle\rangle$ be the target DAS service and let \mathcal{H} be the set of all Multi-DAS-system histories. An Orchestrator for \mathcal{S}_s is a function orc defined as

$$\text{orc} : \mathcal{H} \times \mathcal{A}_t \times \mathcal{B}_t \longrightarrow \mathcal{A}_s \times \mathcal{B}_s$$

such that if $\text{orc}(h, \alpha_t, \sigma_t)$ is defined, i.e. $(\alpha_s, \sigma_s) = \text{orc}(h, \alpha_t, \sigma_t)$, then:

1. $\sigma_t \in \text{ans}(Q_{\alpha_t}, \text{last}(h))$ and $\sigma_s \in \text{ans}(Q_{\alpha_s}, \text{last}(h))$, where $Q_{\alpha_t} \mapsto \alpha_t \in \varrho_t$ and $Q_{\alpha_s} \mapsto \alpha_s \in \varrho_s$;
2. $\text{EFFECTS}(\alpha_t)\sigma_t = \text{EFFECTS}(\alpha_s)\sigma_s$.

Intuitively, an Orchestrator is a function that, given a Multi-DAS-system history, an action that the target service wants to perform with a parameter assignment, returns an action of the Multi-DAS system that is *able* to execute the effects of the target operation. The action of the Multi-DAS system evolves the database as the target action describes. We assume that, at each step, the evaluation of the external service calls, involved in the execution of α_t , is the same applied by the Multi-DAS system.

Definition 14. Let $\mathcal{S}_s = \langle\langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}_s, \mathcal{A}_s, \text{EX}, \varrho_s \rangle\rangle$ be the Multi-DAS system (constituted by the stateless services $\mathcal{S}_i = \langle\langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}_i, \mathcal{A}_i, \varrho_i \rangle\rangle$ for $i \in [1..n]$), let $\mathcal{S}_t = \langle\langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}_t, \mathcal{A}_t, \varrho_t \rangle\rangle$ be the target DAS service and let $\text{orc} : \mathcal{H} \times \mathcal{A}_t \times \mathcal{B}_t \rightarrow \mathcal{A}_s \times \mathcal{B}_s$ be an Orchestrator for \mathcal{S}_s . Given a trace $\tau = \mathcal{I}_0 \xrightarrow{\alpha_t^0 \sigma_t^0} \mathcal{I}_1 \xrightarrow{\alpha_t^1 \sigma_t^1} \mathcal{I}_2 \cdots$ of \mathcal{S}_t , we say that orc realizes τ if and only if for all Multi-DAS-system histories $h \in \mathcal{H}_{\tau, \text{orc}} \subseteq \mathcal{H}$, $\text{orc}(h, \alpha_t^l, \sigma_t^l)$ is defined (with $\text{length}(h) = l$), where the set of Multi-DAS-system histories $\mathcal{H}_{\tau, \text{orc}}$ are defined inductively as follows:

- $h^0 = \mathcal{I}_0 \in \mathcal{H}_{\tau, \text{orc}}$;
- $h^{j+1} \in \mathcal{H}_{\tau, \text{orc}}$ if and only if $h^{j+1} = h^j \xrightarrow{\alpha_s^j \sigma_s^j} \mathcal{I}_{j+1}$, where $h^j \in \mathcal{H}_{\tau, \text{orc}}$ and $\text{orc}(h^j, \alpha_t^j, \sigma_t^j) = (\alpha_s^j, \sigma_s^j)$.

Intuitively, $\mathcal{H}_{\tau, \text{orc}}$ contains only Multi-DAS-system histories that the orchestrator orc generates when instructing the system so to realize τ .

Definition 15. An orchestrator orc for the Multi-DAS system \mathcal{S}_s is a composition of target service \mathcal{S}_t by \mathcal{S}_s if and only if it realizes all \mathcal{S}_t traces.

Definition 16 (Composition Problem). Given a Multi-DAS system $\mathcal{S}_s = \langle\langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}_s, \mathcal{A}_s, \text{EX}, \varrho_s \rangle\rangle$ (constituted by the stateless services $\mathcal{S}_i = \langle\langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}_i, \mathcal{A}_i, \varrho_i \rangle\rangle$ for $i \in [1..n]$) and a deterministic target service $\mathcal{S}_t = \langle\langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}_t, \mathcal{A}_t, \varrho_t \rangle\rangle$, synthesize an orchestrator for \mathcal{S}_s that is a composition of \mathcal{S}_t by \mathcal{S}_s .

6.2.2 Action-Delegation

The problem of computing a composition can be reduced to the problem of calculating the so-called *Action Delegation Relation* between the action set of the target service and the action set of the Multi-DAS system. An Action Delegation Relation is essentially a mapping from the former set to the latter set that associates every target action to a delegate one with the same effect specification. We say that an action α_1 can be delegated to an action α_2 if:

- *the two actions have the same effect specification.* The two actions might be defined with respect to different parameters, so, a *translation* is needed to match the two specifications.
- *when α_1 can be executed with some arguments, it must be always possible to execute α_2 with arguments obtained by applying the parameters translation on the arguments of α_1 .*

Definition 17 (Action-Delegation). Let α_1 and α_2 be two actions, and, let $Q_{\alpha_1}(\vec{p}_1) \mapsto \alpha_1(\vec{p}_1)$, $Q_{\alpha_2}(\vec{p}_2) \mapsto \alpha_2(\vec{p}_2)$ be the CA-Rules associated to α_1 and α_2 , we say that α_1 can be delegated to α_2 , written $\alpha_1 \triangleright \alpha_2$, if:

1. There exists a parameter translation $p_{\alpha_2 \rightarrow \alpha_1}$, that associates every parameters of α_2 to a parameter of α_1 , such that:

$$\text{EFFECTS}(\alpha_1) \stackrel{p_{\alpha_2 \rightarrow \alpha_1}}{\equiv} \text{EFFECTS}(\alpha_2)$$

i.e. under the parameter translation $p_{\alpha_2 \rightarrow \alpha_1}$, the effect specifications of α_1 and α_2 result the same.

2. In every state of the data layer \mathcal{I}^2 must be satisfied the following condition:

$$\theta \in \text{ans}(Q_{\alpha_1}(\vec{p}_1), \mathcal{I}) \implies p_{\alpha_2 \rightarrow \alpha_1}^{-1}(\theta) \in \text{ans}(Q_{\alpha_2}(\vec{p}_2), \mathcal{I})$$

or, equivalently,

$$Q_{\alpha_1}(\vec{p}_1) \implies Q_{\alpha_2}(p_{\alpha_1 \rightarrow \alpha_2}(\vec{p}_2))$$

i.e. if the arguments of α_1 satisfy its CA-Rule, then the translation (through $p_{\alpha_2 \rightarrow \alpha_1}$) of these arguments must satisfy the CA-Rule associated to α_2 .

Example 6.2.1. The Table 6.1 shows an example of actions fulfilling the definition of Action-Delegation. The action α_1 can be delegated to α_2 through

α_1	α_2
$\alpha_1(x,y):\{$ $A(x) \rightsquigarrow \{B(y), C(y)\}$ $D(d) \rightsquigarrow \{E(f(d))\}$ $\}$ $D(x) \wedge E(y) \mapsto \alpha_1(x, y)$	$\alpha_2(z,w,k):\{$ $A(z) \rightsquigarrow \{B(w), C(k)\}$ $D(d) \rightsquigarrow \{E(f(d))\}$ $\}$ $D(z) \wedge E(w) \wedge E(k) \mapsto \alpha_2(z, w, k)$

Table 6.1: Specification of α_1 and α_2

the parameter translation $p_{\alpha_2 \rightarrow \alpha_1}$ defined as follows:

$$p_{\alpha_2 \rightarrow \alpha_1} = \{z \rightarrow x, w \rightarrow y, k \rightarrow y\}$$

The specification of α_2 can be reduced to that of α_1 by applying $p_{\alpha_1 \rightarrow \alpha_2}$. Similarly, the query defined by the CA-Rule of α_2 is reduced to that of α_1 . For instance, when α_1 is invoked by passing the arguments a, b , in order to realize the effects of $\alpha_1(a, b)$, α_2 is to be invoked by passing the arguments (a, b, b) .

²We recall that, the instance of the data layer is shared.

■

It is worth to note that the number of parameters of α_1 can be less than (or, at most equal to) the number of parameters of α_2 . In fact, if this condition is not satisfied, there is no way to assign the parameters of α_2 to those of α_1 . Therefore, the parameter translation can be defined as a non-injective function from the set of variables of α_2 to the set of variables of α_1 . With a slight abuse of notation, we assume that the inverse of such functions can be applied to the parameter assignments of α_1 , so to obtain a parameter assignment for α_2 . In doing so, when a variable of α_1 is assigned to two (or more) variables of α_2 , the inverse of the parameter translation generates for that parameter two (or more) assignments. For instance, consider the Example 6.2.1, $p_{\alpha_2 \rightarrow \alpha_1}^{-1}(\{x \rightarrow a, y \rightarrow b\}) = \{z \rightarrow a, w \rightarrow b, k \rightarrow b\}$. The parameter translation can be applied either on the effect specification of α_2 , or, on the parameter assignments. In the former case, it transforms the the effect specification of α_2 , so to meet that of α_1 . In the latter case, it transforms a parameter assignment defined of α_1 to one of α_2 (by using the inverse).

Given two actions the first condition of the definition 17 can be easily verified by analyzing the two specifications and by finding an appropriate parameter translation. In the worst case, the task of finding the parameter translation takes exponential time in the number of the parameters of the actions.

The second condition is more involving because it need a more sophisticated form of verification. The technique proposed in [9] can verify that, in every state achieved by the system (i.e. a state of the data layer), this implication holds. In order to calculate every possible state, the verification method need to know which actions the system can execute. It is easy to note that, in this approach, the Multi-DAS system performs only the actions whose specification matches one of the target service. Hence, the states (of the data layer) achieved by the Multi-DAS system are only those described by the target service. Furthermore, this method requires that the target service to be data bounded, that is, the states of the data layer (infinite, in general) can be reduced to a finite number of representative instances. This method is necessary in the general case of a complete FOL formula, but there are simpler cases where the implication is easily verified, e.g. when the implication can be expressed through a formula of the Propositional Logic, or, when the guards of the two actions are Conjunctive Queries.

In the following theorem, we prove that executing α_2 with parameters $p_{\alpha_2 \rightarrow \alpha_1}^{-1}(\sigma)$ against a database instance \mathcal{I} , causes the same updates of performing α_1 with parameters σ against \mathcal{I} .

Theorem 6. *Given two actions α_1 and α_2 , defined over the same data layer, if $\alpha_1 \triangleright \alpha_2$ through a parameter translation $p_{\alpha_2 \rightarrow \alpha_1}$, we have that for every \mathcal{I} and valid parameter assignment σ for α_1 over \mathcal{I} :*

$$DO(\mathcal{I}, \alpha_1, \sigma) = DO(\mathcal{I}, \alpha_2, p_{\alpha_2 \rightarrow \alpha_1}^{-1}(\sigma))$$

Proof. First, by the definition 17, if α_1 can be executed over \mathcal{I} with a parameter assignment σ , then α_2 can be executed over \mathcal{I} with a parameter assignment

$p_{\alpha_2 \rightarrow \alpha_1}^{-1}(\sigma)$. Moreover, by definition of Action-Delegation, the parameter translation $p_{\alpha_2 \rightarrow \alpha_1}$ is defined so to transform the effect specification of α_2 to that of α_1 , therefore, for each $p_i^1 \rightsquigarrow \{add_i^1, del_i^1\} \in \text{EFFECTS}(\alpha_1)$ there exists an effect of α_2 $p_i^2 \rightsquigarrow \{add_i^2, del_i^2\} \in \text{EFFECTS}(\alpha_2)$, such that, $p_{\alpha_2 \rightarrow \alpha_1}(p_i^2) = p_i^1$ and $p_{\alpha_2 \rightarrow \alpha_1}(\{add_i^2, del_i^2\}) = \{add_i^1, del_i^1\}$. Equivalently, for each parameter assignment σ for α_1 there exists a $p_i^2 \rightsquigarrow \{add_i^2, del_i^2\} \in \text{EFFECTS}(\alpha_2)$ such that $p_i^1 \sigma = p_i^2 p_{\alpha_2 \rightarrow \alpha_1}^{-1}(\sigma)$ and $\{add_i^1, del_i^1\} \sigma = \{add_i^2, del_i^2\} p_{\alpha_2 \rightarrow \alpha_1}^{-1}(\sigma)$. Therefore, from the definition 3.1:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{DO}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha_1, \sigma) &= (\mathcal{I} - \bigcup_{p_i^1 \rightsquigarrow \{add_i^1, del_i^1\} \in \text{EFFECTS}(\alpha_1)} \bigcup_{\theta \in \text{ans}(p_i^1 \sigma, \mathcal{I})} \bigcup_{del_{ij}^1 \in del_i^1} del_{ij}^1 \sigma \theta) \\
&\quad \bigcup_{p_i^1 \rightsquigarrow \{add_i^1, del_i^1\} \in \text{EFFECTS}(\alpha_1)} \bigcup_{\theta \in \text{ans}(p_i^1 \sigma, \mathcal{I})} \bigcup_{add_{ij}^1 \in add_i^1} add_{ij}^1 \sigma \theta = \\
&(\mathcal{I} - \bigcup_{p_i^2 \rightsquigarrow \{add_i^2, del_i^2\} \in \text{EFFECTS}(\alpha_2)} \bigcup_{\theta \in \text{ans}(p_i^2 p_{\alpha_2 \rightarrow \alpha_1}^{-1}(\sigma), \mathcal{I})} \bigcup_{d_{ij}^2 \in del_i^2} d_{ij}^2 p_{\alpha_2 \rightarrow \alpha_1}^{-1}(\sigma) \theta) \\
&\quad \bigcup_{p_i^2 \rightsquigarrow \{add_i^2, del_i^2\} \in \text{EFFECTS}(\alpha_2)} \bigcup_{\theta \in \text{ans}(p_i^2 p_{\alpha_2 \rightarrow \alpha_1}^{-1}(\sigma), \mathcal{I})} \bigcup_{a_{ij}^2 \in add_i^2} a_{ij}^2 p_{\alpha_2 \rightarrow \alpha_1}^{-1}(\sigma) \theta = \\
&= \text{DO}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha_2, p_{\alpha_2 \rightarrow \alpha_1}^{-1}(\sigma))
\end{aligned}$$

□

Definition 18 (Action-Delegation Relation). Given two action sets \mathcal{A}_1 and \mathcal{A}_2 , the *Action-Delegation Relation* \mathfrak{D} from \mathcal{A}_1 to \mathcal{A}_2 is defined as $\mathfrak{D} \subseteq \mathcal{A}_1 \times \mathcal{A}_2$, such that $(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) \in \mathfrak{D}$ iff $\alpha_1 \triangleright \alpha_2$.

Definition 19 (Action-Delegation Problem). Given two DASs $\mathcal{S}_1 = \langle \langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{A}_1, \varrho_1, \mathbb{S}_1, s_0^1, \delta_1, \mathbb{F}_1 \rangle \rangle$ and $\mathcal{S}_2 = \langle \langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}_2, \mathcal{A}_2, \varrho_2, \mathbb{S}_2, s_0^2, \delta_2, \mathbb{F}_2 \rangle \rangle$, the Action-Delegation Problem is the problem of finding an Action-Delegation Relation \mathfrak{D} from \mathcal{A}_1 to \mathcal{A}_2 .

A solution of the Action-Delegation problem is an Action-Delegation Relation \mathfrak{D} . Once the relation is computed, in any state of the data layer, the execution of any action of \mathcal{S}_1 can be delegated to, at least, an action of \mathcal{S}_2 .

6.2.3 Action-Delegator

In the stateless setting, the service composition purpose is enacted by a very simple software component, called *Action-Delegator*. Indeed, there is no need of a convoluted Orchestrator, it has to accomplish the tasks of capturing the target request, and, invoking an action designed by the Action-Delegator.

The Action-Delegator is a component intended to associate each target action to (at least) a delegate action (of the Multi-DAS system). It provides a delegate action that realizes a target specification in every state of the data layer. The delegate action guarantees that the database evolves as described by the target action. It can be automatically generated from the Action-Delegation Relation.

In order to formalize the Action-Delegator, we need to define the set containing all possible parameter translations. Given two action sets \mathcal{A}_1 and \mathcal{A}_2 , the set

$\mathbb{P}_{\mathcal{A}_2 \rightarrow \mathcal{A}_1}$, containing all possible parameter translations for the actions of \mathcal{A}_2 to the actions of \mathcal{A}_1 , is defined as follows:

$$\mathbb{P}_{\mathcal{A}_2 \rightarrow \mathcal{A}_1} = \{ \mathbb{p}_{\alpha_2 \rightarrow \alpha_1} \mid \alpha_1 \in \mathcal{A}_1 \text{ and } \alpha_2 \in \mathcal{A}_2 \\ \alpha_1 \triangleright \alpha_2 \text{ through } \mathbb{p}_{\alpha_2 \rightarrow \alpha_1} \}$$

Definition 20 (Action-Delegator). Given two stateless DASs $\mathcal{S}_1 = \langle \langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{A}_1, \varrho_1 \rangle \rangle$ and $\mathcal{S}_2 = \langle \langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}_2, \mathcal{A}_2, \varrho_2 \rangle \rangle$, an *Action-Delegator* for \mathcal{S}_1 to \mathcal{S}_2 is a total function $\mathfrak{del} : \mathcal{A}_1 \rightarrow 2^{\mathcal{A}_2 \times \mathbb{P}_{\mathcal{A}_2 \rightarrow \mathcal{A}_1}}$, where $(\alpha_2, \mathbb{p}_{\alpha_2 \rightarrow \alpha_1}) \in \mathfrak{del}(\alpha_1)$ if and only if $\alpha_1 \triangleright \alpha_2$ through $\mathbb{p}_{\alpha_2 \rightarrow \alpha_1}$.

Definition 21 (Data-Aware Service Composition problem in stateless setting). Given a Multi-DAS System $\mathcal{S}_s = \langle \langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}_s, \mathcal{A}_s, \text{EX}, \varrho_s \rangle \rangle$ and a target service $\mathcal{S}_t = \langle \langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}_t, \mathcal{A}_t, \varrho_t \rangle \rangle$, synthesize an Action-Delegator \mathfrak{del} for \mathcal{S}_t to \mathcal{S}_s , that delegates the execution of the actions of \mathcal{S}_t to \mathcal{S}_s .

In every state of the data layer, the execution of an action $\alpha_t \in \mathcal{A}_t$, with a valid parameter assignment σ , can be delegated to the execution an action α_s of the Multi-DAS system in $\mathfrak{del}(\alpha_t)$. In details, by the theorem 6, if $(\alpha_s, \mathbb{p}_{\alpha_s \rightarrow \alpha_t}) \in \mathfrak{del}(\alpha_t)$, then, for any \mathcal{I} and for any valid assignment σ for the parameters of α_t , the execution of α_t over \mathcal{I} with parameter σ is equivalent to the the execution of α_s over \mathcal{I} with a parameter assignment $\mathbb{p}_{\alpha_s \rightarrow \alpha_t}^{-1}(\sigma)$, i.e. $\text{DO}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha_t, \sigma) = \text{DO}(\mathcal{I}, \alpha_s, \mathbb{p}_{\alpha_s \rightarrow \alpha_t}^{-1}(\sigma))$. Given an Action-Delegation Relation \mathfrak{D} , the Action-Delegator \mathfrak{del} is responsible to query \mathfrak{D} for obtaining the appropriate action delegates. In this scenario, when the target service requests for the execution of α_t with a parameter assignment σ , the Orchestrator has to retrieve from the Action-Delegator the delegates of α_t , i.e. $\mathfrak{del}(\alpha_t)$. Then, the Orchestrator chooses a delegate α_s from $\mathfrak{del}(\alpha_t)$, i.e. $(\alpha_s, \mathbb{p}_{\alpha_s \rightarrow \alpha_t}^{-1}) \in \mathfrak{del}(\alpha_t)$, and, finally, it realizes the specification of α_t by requesting to $\text{EX}(\alpha_s)$ the execution of α_s with a parameter assignment $\mathbb{p}_{\alpha_s \rightarrow \alpha_t}^{-1}(\sigma)$.

6.3 Stateful Setting

In the stateful setting, a DAS is defined by $\mathcal{S} = \langle \langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{A}, \varrho, \mathbb{S}, s_0, \delta, \mathbb{F} \rangle \rangle$. Therefore, in addition to the CA-Rules, the action execution is constrained by a transition system which specifies the sequences of atomic actions that a service can perform. At each step, the Orchestrator has to choose only delegate actions available in the current process state of the Multi-DAS system.

In the stateful setting, a composition exists when: in every possible state, if the target service can execute an action α_t (with some arguments), then the Multi-DAS system must be able to perform an action α_s that realizes the effect specification of α_t . In this case, the execution of an action evolves both the data layer and the process of a service. Since both components affects the action execution, they are to be taken into account in the verification of the existence of a composition.

Therefore, it can be defined two different problem concerning the composition synthesis. The first is the *Action Delegation Problem*, i.e. the problem of

finding, for each target action, there exists an action of the Multi-DAS system that realizes (in every state of the data layer) its specification. Since every conversation with a stateful service can be mimed by the stateless service derived to it (cf. 3.4), we noticed that the technique developed for the stateless case can be applied in the stateful case. Once the Action Delegation Relation is computed, to every action of the target service it is associated (at least) an action of the Multi-DAS system that can execute its specification. But, differently from the stateless case, this delegation can be accomplished only if the Multi-DAS system is in a process state that allows to execute the delegate action.

This issue is matter of the *Behavioral Composition Problem*. This problem is concerned with checking that, in every possible process state, every available target action has an available action-delegate. In order to tackle this issue, we recur to the same approach showed in the Roman Model which is based on the notion of simulation. We recall that, given two transition systems S and S' , S simulates S' if, intuitively, every (possibly infinite) of S' is also a path of S . Therefore, if the transition system of the Multi-DAS system simulates the transition system of the target service, then the system is able to realize all possible target conversations. The difference between the two approaches is the method for matching the transitions. In the Roman Model two transitions match when they have the same name, instead, in our approach the target action matches only with actions associated to it through the Action-Delegation Relation.

In the stateful setting, the enactment of the Service Composition schema requires a slightly more complicated Orchestrator respect to the previous case. The Orchestrator has to monitor the process state of the Multi-DAS system and, then, it has to invoke delegate actions that are compliant with it. To be more precise, according to its current state, the target service proposes to the client a set of available actions; the client selects one of such actions; the request for the selected action is captured by the Orchestrator; the Orchestrator get from the Action Delegator the delegate-actions for the requested action; finally, the Orchestrator invokes the execution of a delegate-action according to the current state of the Multi-DAS system.

6.3.1 Service Composition in stateful setting

To formally define the service composition we recur to the semantics defined in the Chapter 3.

Definition 22 (Trace). Given a stateless service $\mathcal{S} = \langle \langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{A}, \varrho, \mathbb{S}, s_0, \delta, \mathbb{F} \rangle \rangle$, a trace for \mathcal{S} is a possible infinite sequence of alternating state of the service (made up of a database instance and a process state), and, instantiated actions. A trace has the form:

$$\langle \mathcal{I}_0, s^0 \rangle \xrightarrow{\alpha_0 \sigma^0} \mathcal{S} \langle \mathcal{I}_1, s^1 \rangle \xrightarrow{\alpha_1 \sigma^1} \mathcal{S} \langle \mathcal{I}_2, s^2 \rangle \dots$$

such that:

1. $\langle \mathcal{I}_0, s^0 \rangle = \langle \mathcal{I}_0, s_0 \rangle$
2. for all j , $\langle \mathcal{I}_j, s^j \rangle \xrightarrow{\alpha_j \sigma^j} \mathcal{S} \langle \mathcal{I}_{j+1}, s^{j+1} \rangle$ in $\Upsilon_{\mathcal{S}}^3$;

The definition of history is the same as the previous case. Now, we can provide the definition of Orchestrator.

Definition 23 (Orchestrator). Let $\mathcal{S}_s = \langle \langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}_s, \mathcal{A}_s, \text{EX}, \varrho_s, \mathbb{S}_s, s_0^s, \delta_s, \mathbb{F}_s \rangle \rangle$ be the Multi-DAS system (constituted by the stateless services $\mathcal{S}_i = \langle \langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}_i, \mathcal{A}_i, \varrho_i, \mathbb{S}_i, s_0^i, \delta_i, \mathbb{F}_i \rangle \rangle$ for $i \in [1..n]$), let $\mathcal{S}_t = \langle \langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}_t, \mathcal{A}_t, \varrho_t, \mathbb{S}_t, s_0^t, \delta_t, \mathbb{F}_t \rangle \rangle$ be a target DAS service, and let \mathcal{H} be the set of all Multi-DAS-system histories. An Orchestrator for \mathcal{S}_s is a function orc defined as

$$\text{orc} : \mathcal{H} \times \mathcal{A}_t \times \mathcal{B}_t \longrightarrow \mathcal{A}_s \times \mathcal{B}_s$$

such that if $\text{orc}(h, \alpha_t, \sigma_t)$ is defined, i.e. $(\alpha_s, \sigma_s) = \text{orc}(h, \alpha_t, \sigma_t)$, then:

1. $\sigma_t \in \text{ans}(Q_{\alpha_t}, \text{db}_{\mathcal{S}_s}(\text{last}(h)))$ and $\sigma_s \in \text{ans}(Q_{\alpha_s}, \text{db}_{\mathcal{S}_s}(\text{last}(h)))$, where $Q_{\alpha_t} \mapsto \alpha_t \in \varrho_t$ and $Q_{\alpha_s} \mapsto \alpha_s \in \varrho_s$;
2. α_s can be executed in $\text{pst}_{\mathcal{S}_s}(\text{last}(h))$;
3. $\text{EFFECTS}(\alpha_t)\sigma_t = \text{EFFECTS}(\alpha_s)\sigma_s$.

Intuitively, an orchestrator is a function that, given a Multi-DAS-system history, an action that the target service wants to perform with a parameter assignment, returns an action of the Multi-DAS system that is *able* to execute the effects of the target operation. The action of the Multi-DAS system evolves the database as the target action describes. We assume that, at each step, the evaluation of the external service calls, involved in the execution of α_t , is the same applied by the Multi-DAS system.

Definition 24. Let $\mathcal{S}_s = \langle \langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}_s, \mathcal{A}_s, \text{EX}, \varrho_s, \mathbb{S}_s, s_0^s, \delta_s, \mathbb{F}_s \rangle \rangle$ be the Multi-DAS system (constituted by the stateless services $\mathcal{S}_i = \langle \langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}_i, \mathcal{A}_i, \varrho_i, \mathbb{S}_i, s_0^i, \delta_i, \mathbb{F}_i \rangle \rangle$ for $i \in [1..n]$), let $\mathcal{S}_t = \langle \langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}_t, \mathcal{A}_t, \varrho_t, \mathbb{S}_t, s_0^t, \delta_t, \mathbb{F}_t \rangle \rangle$ be the target DAS service, and let $\text{orc} : \mathcal{H} \times \mathcal{A}_t \times \mathcal{B}_t \longrightarrow \mathcal{A}_s \times \mathcal{B}_s$ be an Orchestrator for \mathcal{S}_s . Given a trace $\tau = \langle \mathcal{I}_0, s^0 \rangle \xrightarrow{\alpha_0 \sigma^0} \mathcal{S} \langle \mathcal{I}_1, s^1 \rangle \xrightarrow{\alpha_1 \sigma^1} \mathcal{S} \langle \mathcal{I}_2, s^2 \rangle \cdots \mathcal{I}_1 \xrightarrow{\alpha_l^1 \sigma_l^1} \mathcal{S}_t \mathcal{I}_2 \cdots$ of \mathcal{S}_t , we say that orc realizes τ if and only if for all Multi-DAS-system histories $h \in \mathcal{H}_{\tau, \text{orc}} \subseteq \mathcal{H}$, $\text{orc}(h, \alpha_t^l, \sigma_t^l)$ is defined ($\text{length}(h) = l$), where the set of Multi-DAS-system histories $\mathcal{H}_{\tau, \text{orc}}$ are defined inductively as follows:

- $h^0 = \langle \mathcal{I}_0, s_0 \rangle \in \mathcal{H}_{\tau, \text{orc}}$;
- $h^{j+1} \in \mathcal{H}_{\tau, \text{orc}}$ if and only if $h^{j+1} = h^j \xrightarrow{\alpha_s^j \sigma_s^j} \mathcal{S}_s \langle \mathcal{I}_{j+1}, s^{j+1} \rangle$, where $h^j \in \mathcal{H}_{\tau, \text{orc}}$ and $\text{orc}(h^j, \alpha_t^j, \sigma_t^j) = (\alpha_s^j, \sigma_s^j)$.

³We assume that \mathcal{S} uses non-deterministic external services.

Intuitively, $\mathcal{H}_{\tau, \text{orc}}$ contains only Multi-DAS-system histories that the orchestrator orc generates when instructing the system so to realize τ .

Definition 25. An orchestrator orc for the Multi-DAS system \mathcal{S}_s is a composition of target service \mathcal{S}_t by \mathcal{S}_s if and only if it realizes all \mathcal{S}_t traces.

Definition 26 (Composition Problem). Given a Multi-DAS system $\mathcal{S}_s = \langle \langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}_s, \mathcal{A}_s, \varrho_s, \mathbb{S}_s, s_0^s, \delta_s, \mathbb{F}_s \rangle \rangle$ (constituted by the stateless services $\mathcal{S}_i = \langle \langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}_i, \mathcal{A}_i, \varrho_i, \mathbb{S}_i, s_0^i, \delta_i, \mathbb{F}_i \rangle \rangle$ for $i \in [1..n]$) and a deterministic target service $\mathcal{S}_t = \langle \langle \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{I}_0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{F}_t, \mathcal{A}_t, \varrho_t, \mathbb{S}_t, s_0^t, \delta_t, \mathbb{F}_t \rangle \rangle$, synthesize an orchestrator for \mathcal{S}_s that is a composition of \mathcal{S}_t by \mathcal{S}_s .

6.3.2 Composition via the relations of Simulation and Action-Delegation

In this section we present our approach for synthesizing a composition, based on the notions of simulation and action-delegation. Intuitively, a Multi-DAS system \mathcal{S}_s simulates a DAS \mathcal{S}_t if \mathcal{S}_s is able to match, step-by-step, all \mathcal{S}_t data-layer evolutions. In the *stateless setting*, we showed that to every action α_t of \mathcal{S}_t can be associated, through the Action-Delegation Relation, to an action α_s of \mathcal{S}_s that is able to realize, in every data-layer state, the specification of α_t . Therefore, the approach devised in the stateless case gives us the ability of matching an execution step of the target service with an execution of the Multi-DAS system. This is a local condition, i.e. it deals with a single execution step. In order to deal with the entire evolutions, we need to introduce a novel notion of *simulation*, called ADEL-Simulation. Differently from the ND-Simulation of the Roman Model, the ADEL-Simulation matches the transitions that are compliant with the Action-Delegation Relation.

Definition 27. An ADEL-Simulation of \mathcal{S}_t by \mathcal{S}_s is a relation $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathbb{S}_t \times \mathbb{S}_s$, where $\langle s_t, s_s \rangle \in \mathcal{S}$, if for all $\alpha_t \in \mathcal{A}_t$ there exists an $\alpha_s \in \mathcal{A}_s$ such that:

1. there exists a parameter translation $\text{p}_{\alpha_s \rightarrow \alpha_t}$ such that $(\alpha_s, \text{p}_{\alpha_s \rightarrow \alpha_t}) \in \text{del}(\alpha_t)$;
2. for all transitions $\langle s_t, \alpha_t, s'_t \rangle \in \delta_t$:
 - there exists a transition $\langle s_s, \alpha_s, s'_s \rangle \in \delta_s$; and
 - for all transitions $\langle s_s, \alpha_s, s'_s \rangle \in \delta_s$, we have $\langle s'_t, s'_s \rangle \in \mathcal{S}$.

It is worth noting that, an ADEL-Simulation simulation can be easily derived starting from the Action-Delegation Relation from \mathcal{A}_t to \mathcal{A}_s and the Simulation Relation between the transition system of the target service and that of the Multi-DAS system. In addition to the conditions defining a Simulation, an ADEL-Simulation requires that every transition of target service is matched, through the Action-Delegation Relation, to a transition of the Multi-DAS system.

With an ADEL-Simulation we can synthesize an Orchestrator for the Multi-DAS system \mathcal{S}_s . Let \mathcal{D} be the Action-Delegation Relation from \mathcal{A}_t to the \mathcal{A}_s ,

\mathfrak{del} be the *Action-Delegator* generated by it, \mathcal{S} be the ADEL-Simulation between states of \mathcal{S}_t and \mathcal{S}_s . The *Orchestrator Generator* of \mathcal{S}_s for \mathcal{S}_t is a tuple defined as:

$$\mathcal{OG} = \langle \Sigma, \mathcal{A}_t, \mathcal{A}_s, \mathbb{P}_{\mathcal{A}_s \rightarrow \mathcal{A}_t}, \partial, \omega \rangle$$

where:

- $\Sigma = \{ \langle s_t, s_s \rangle \in \mathbb{S}_{\mathcal{S}_t} \times \mathbb{S}_{\mathcal{S}_s} \mid s_t \preceq s_s \}$ is the set of states of \mathcal{OG} , formed by those pair of $\mathbb{S}_{\mathcal{S}_t}$ and $\mathbb{S}_{\mathcal{S}_s}$ that are in \mathcal{S} , given a state $\varsigma = \langle s_t, s_s \rangle \in \Sigma$ we denote s_t con $com_{\mathcal{S}_t}(\varsigma)$ e s_s con $com_{\mathcal{S}_s}(\varsigma)$;
- \mathcal{A}_t and \mathcal{A}_s are, respectively, the action sets of the target service and the Multi-DAS system;
- $\mathbb{P}_{\mathcal{A}_s \rightarrow \mathcal{A}_t}$ is the finite set containing all possible parameter translation for the actions of \mathcal{S}_s to the actions of \mathcal{S}_t ;
- $\partial \subseteq \Sigma \times \mathcal{A}_t \times \Sigma$ is the transition relation for \mathcal{OG} , where $\langle \varsigma, \alpha_t, \varsigma' \rangle \in \partial$ if and only if there exist α_s and $\mathbb{p}_{\alpha_s \rightarrow \alpha_t}$ such that:

- $\langle com_{\mathcal{S}_t}(\varsigma), \alpha_t, com_{\mathcal{S}_t}(\varsigma') \rangle \in \delta_{\mathcal{S}_t}$
- $\langle com_{\mathcal{S}_s}(\varsigma), \alpha_s, com_{\mathcal{S}_s}(\varsigma') \rangle \in \delta_{\mathcal{S}_s}$
- for all $\langle com_{\mathcal{S}_s}(\varsigma), \alpha_s, s'_{\mathcal{S}_s} \rangle \in \delta_{\mathcal{S}_s}$, $\langle com_{\mathcal{S}_t}(\varsigma'), s'_{\mathcal{S}_s} \rangle \in \Sigma$
- $(\alpha_s, \mathbb{p}_{\alpha_s \rightarrow \alpha_t}) \in \mathfrak{del}(\alpha_t)$;

- $\omega : \Sigma \times \mathcal{A}_t \rightarrow 2^{\mathcal{A}_s \times \mathbb{P}_{\mathcal{A}_s \rightarrow \mathcal{A}_t}}$, where:

$$\begin{aligned} \omega(\varsigma, \alpha_t) = \{ (\alpha_s, \mathbb{p}_{\alpha_s \rightarrow \alpha_t}) \mid \exists \varsigma' \text{ s.t. } \langle \varsigma, \alpha_t, \varsigma' \rangle \in \partial \text{ and} \\ (\alpha_s, \mathbb{p}_{\alpha_s \rightarrow \alpha_t}) \in \mathfrak{del}(\alpha_t) \text{ and} \\ \langle com_{\mathcal{S}_s}(\varsigma), \alpha_s, com_{\mathcal{S}_s}(\varsigma') \rangle \in \delta_{\mathcal{S}_s} \text{ and} \\ \forall \langle com_{\mathcal{S}_s}(\varsigma), \alpha_s, s'_{\mathcal{S}_s} \rangle \in \delta_{\mathcal{S}_s}. \langle com_{\mathcal{S}_t}(\varsigma'), s'_{\mathcal{S}_s} \rangle \in \Sigma \} \end{aligned}$$

The Orchestrator Generator is a finite state transducer that, given an action α_t of \mathcal{S}_t , outputs through ω , according to actual system state, the set of all actions α_s of \mathcal{S}_s , that are *available* in the current state of the system, that *realize* the effect specification of α_t and that *preserve* the simulation. The output function returns together with each the action α_s , a parameter translation $\mathbb{p}_{\alpha_s \rightarrow \alpha_t}$ that instructs on how to invoke the action α_s so to realize the effects of α_t . Once the Simulation Relation and the Action-Delegation relations are computed, the synthesis of the Orchestrator Generator involves only local conditions. The actual Orchestrator can be obtained by picking, at each step, one pair $(\alpha_s, \mathbb{p}_{\alpha_s \rightarrow \alpha_t})$ among those returned by ω , and, then, by applying $\mathbb{p}_{\alpha_s \rightarrow \alpha_t}^{-1}$ on the parameter assignment given as input of the Orchestrator.

6.4 Discussion

In this Chapter, we have provided the solution techniques for computing a data-aware service composition in the case of a common data-layer shared by the available services and the target service. We have devised a technique for solving the issues regarding the data aspects arisen by the composition problem. Specifically, the approach is based on the notion of Action-Delegation which is concerned with finding among the action set of the Multi-DAS system, an action that executes a desired effect specification. We have showed how to compute the so-called Action-Delegation Relation, that associates to every target action, a Multi-DAS system delegate. Finally, we have defined a procedure for automatically synthesizing a composition of data-aware services that share a common data layer. This synthesis is made up of two distinct elements, the Action-Delegation Relation between the action set of the target and the action set of the Multi-DAS system; and, the Simulation Relation between the transition system of the target service and that of Multi-DAS system. This approach has the advantage of computing the composition synthesis by exploiting well-known tools, namely, a theorem prover for the Action-Delegation Relation and the composition engine (as proposed in the Roman Model) for Simulation Relation. The Action-Delegator and the Orchestrator program are automatically generated starting from the composition synthesis. These components guarantee the correct execution of the composite service. In particular, the Orchestrator captures the request for a target action, it retrieves from the Action-Delegator a set of actions suitable for delegation, and, it invokes the execution of a delegate action that is available in the actual state of the Multi-DAS system.

Chapter 7

Conclusions and Future Work

7.1 Conclusions

In this thesis we have defined a formal framework for the characterization and theoretical investigation of the problem of *data-aware service composition*, in the special case of services sharing a common data layer. We have drawn inspiration mainly from: the “Roman Model” [14, 15, 22] for a complete characterization of the Service Composition problem; and, from the latest studies on modeling and analysis of Business Processes [19, 9] for describing the service behavior.

First, we focused on the service modeling issue. We needed a formalism that, on the one hand, was able to describe the behavior of services by paying more attention (with respect to the existing proposals) on the data involved in the service execution, and, on the other hand, allows the verification of sophisticated temporal properties. These aspects are, mainly, embodied by DCDS [9] which forms the foundation of our formalism, called DAS. Such model allows to capture the dynamic capabilities of services and specifies how its execution affects (or, is affected by) a full-fledged database. Furthermore, this formalism gives the possibility of describing a wide range of real scenarios.

Second, we devised a technique for solving the issues regarding the data aspects arisen by the composition problem. Specifically, the approach is based on the *Action-Delegation* notion which is concerned with finding among available services an action that executes a desired effect specification. We proposed a procedure that is able to compute the so-called *Action-Delegation Relation*, that associates to every target action, a community-action delegate. From this relation, we built a software component called *Action-Delegator* which suitably invokes the execution of the action delegates.

Third, we noticed that the composition scenario and the action-delegation method allow to reach a new level of composition techniques, in which the actions of the available services are combined (in order to be invoked together) for deriving new composite actions. From an external point of view the composite actions act as the atomic ones. This mechanism allowed to extend the community capabilities

by introducing new actions that are derived from the existing ones. We provided a formal specification of actions that are suitable for combination and we devised a straightforward syntactic condition able to check if the component actions can be executed together. This approach represents a significant improvement with respect to the existing composition techniques where the target actions are delegated to a single action of an available service. We showed that, in a stateless setting, the *Action-Delegator* is the main component that is needed to enact the service composition scenario.

Finally, we proposed a technique for automatically synthesizing a composition of data-aware services that share a common data layer. This synthesis is made up of two distinct elements, the *Action-Delegation Relation* between the action set of the target and the action set of the community; and, the *Simulation Relation* between the transition system of the target service and the transition system of the community. This approach has the advantage of computing the composition synthesis by exploiting well-known tools, namely, a theorem prover for the Action-Delegation Relation and the composition engine (as proposed in the Roman Model) for Simulation Relation. The Action-Delegator and the Orchestrator program are automatically generated starting from the composition synthesis. These components guarantee the correct execution of the composite service. In particular, the Orchestrator captures the request for a target action, it retrieves from the Action-Delegator a set of actions suitable for delegation, and, it invokes the execution of a delegate action that is available in the actual state of the Multi-DAS system.

Below, we summarize our main contributions with respect to the research on Service Oriented Computing:

- Presenting a formalism for service behavioral description, that is able to represent a variety of dynamics with the peculiarity of capturing the data-management capabilities of the process implemented by the service;
- Defining the data-aware service composition problem in presence of a shared data layer;
- Introducing the notion of action-delegation;
- Devising an approach to the data-aware service composition that allows to tackle static aspects (i.e. the data layer evolves as defined in the target service specification) separately from dynamic aspects (i.e. the execution of a target action is always delegated to the community);
- Providing a technique for computing the composition synthesis in the special case when both composite and component services share a common data layer;

7.2 Future Work

The research areas related to data-aware process analysis, and in particular, data-aware service composition are quite recent and there are many open problems to

study and resolve. The work done in this thesis can be therefore taken as starting point for a deeper investigation of several aspects related to the problem. In the next Sections, we discuss additional extensions that we are currently developing.

7.2.1 Merging action-delegation and orchestration

In this thesis we suggested a distinction between static and dynamic aspects concerning the composition, and consequently, we proposed solution techniques supporting this vision. The static aspects are addressed by the Action-Delegation, whereas, the dynamic ones are faced through a Simulation-based solution. But, it can be followed an alternative approach for synthesizing a data-aware composition in which the two aspects are tackled together. The idea at the basis of this method is to simulate the execution of the system and to check if, in every achieved state, it is always possible to delegate the execution of a target action to a community one. Due to the data layer, the number of states achieved by the system is generally infinite. Therefore, it is necessary a reduction to a finite set of system situations¹ which are representative of all possible situations that the system can possibly achieve.

Example 7.2.1. This simple Example highlights a case where the approach proposed in this thesis fails, but this alternative method succeeds. Consider the following target action:

$$\alpha_t():\{ \\ A(x) \rightsquigarrow B(x); \\ C(x) \rightsquigarrow D(x); \\ \}$$

Assume that, in the current process state it is only available the following community action:

$$\alpha_c():\{ \\ A(x) \rightsquigarrow B(x); \\ \}$$

Finally, suppose that $\mathcal{I} = \{A(a)\}$ is the actual data-layer instance. By adopting the proposed method, the action α_t cannot be delegated to α_c . Clearly, this is true in the general case because the execution of α_c does not cause the effect $C(x) \rightsquigarrow D(x)$. But, in the specific situation where the state of the data layer is represented by \mathcal{I} , the effects of α_t are fully realized by α_c . ■

¹We recall that, a situation is defined by the actual state of the data layer and the process states of the target service and the available services.

Figure 7.1: Multitarget composition phases

The example 7.2.1 shows how the action-delegation mechanism takes advantage of this new method, but, similar interesting benefits could be achieved in the verification of the implications issued by the delegation task.

A simulation-based technique might be developed for synthesizing a composition. The solution method could simulate the execution of the system, and, check that in each state every target action has a community delegate. The difference with the former proposal is the mechanism for matching the two action specifications. In the former proposal, the matching has to be valid for each possible data layer instance. Instead, in this case, the matching is verified with respect to the data layer instance on which the action is executed, and, it has to be valid for *only* this instance.

7.2.2 Multitarget composition

Allowing the simultaneous execution of multiple target services over the same available community is an interesting extension that might be supported by our framework. These targets are meant to act autonomously and asynchronously on a shared database. An example of multitarget composition acting on a shared environment can be found in [21]. The Figure 7.1 schematizes respectively the composition and the orchestration scenario in a multi-target environment. The (overall) behavior to be realized by the community depends on the interleaving of the individual target behaviors. Indeed, it is possible to define two communities, the *target community* and the *available community*. As done for the available community, it is necessary to define the overall behavior of the target community for specifying the conversations it can enact. In the multitarget case, a composition exists, if every fragment of the execution of the target community can be delegated to the available community.

Figure 7.2: Aspects of the composition with service-own data layers.

With this approach the target community can be viewed as a single target service, but we identify an issue that suggest to maintain the distinction within target services. In the single-target case, the resources (in our case, the database) are intended to be managed by a single entity which operates and, then, get responses from it; but, in the multiple target case, the effects of an action executed by a target system might be modified (by another target) before it get the results. This is due to the nature of operations modeled. In fact, the proposed formalism models only the updates and ignores the read operations. A strategy to overcome this issue might be specifying the read operations and imposing a scheduling that includes both read and update operations issued by the services. The purpose of this schedule is to enqueue the operations coming from the same target system, so to allow the service to get the results of its operations (Figure 7.1b).

7.2.3 Non-shared data layer

This thesis represents a solution of the problem of the data-aware service composition, in the particular case of services that are defined with respect to the same data layer, and, acting on top of a shared database. Formulating and facing the problem in the general case of service-owner data layer is the next step to be accomplished. The figure 7.2a shows the main features of this new composition scenario. The community is formed by N available services, each of these accesses to its own database. Each database follows a possibly different data schema. The available services publish their behavior described in a data-aware formalism. As usual, the target defines the desired data layer (that it is, possibly, different from the available ones) and the desired action layer. A possible approach to tackle

the problem could be reconciling the available data schemas through a mapping and trying to use the well-known techniques developed for the shared data layer case. The mapping issue is related to the research area of Data-Integration. In the literature two approaches have been proposed for specifying the mapping, they are called *GAV* (Global-as-view) and *LAV* (Local-as-view) [27]. Clearly, in our case, the global schema is defined by the target data layer, whereas, the source schemas are obtained from the data layer of the available services (cf. the Figure 7.2b).

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